

D6.4 Mid-term Data Management Plan

Prepared by: UOULU

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Table of Contents

Version History	1
Deliverable Information	1
Table of Contents	2
List of Tables	5
Acronyms and Abbreviations	6
1 Introduction	9
1.1 Scope	9
1.2 Purpose.....	9
1.3 DMP Methodology.....	9
2 Data Summary	10
2.1 WP1: Assessment of pollution sources, distribution, and impacts in Arctic ecosystems.....	10
2.1.1 Description.....	10
2.1.2 Data summary for WP1.....	11
2.1.3 To whom the data might be useful.....	15
2.1.4 Possibility of integration and re-use	15
2.2 WP2: Risk assessment and local resilience strategies for ecosystems and communities in response to pollution	15
2.2.1 Description.....	15
2.2.2 Data summary for WP2.....	16
2.2.3 To whom the data might be useful.....	28
2.2.4 Possibility of integration and re-use	28
2.3 WP3: Facilitating effective science-based pollution-control governance.....	28
2.3.1 Description.....	28
2.3.2 Data summary for WP3.....	29
2.3.3 To whom the data might be useful.....	32
2.3.4 Possibility of integration and re-use	32
2.4 WP4: Co-Creation, Ethics, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion	32
2.4.1 Description.....	32
2.4.2 Data summary for WP4.....	33
2.4.3 To whom the data might be useful.....	39
2.4.4 Possibility of integration and re-use	39
2.5 WP5: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach	39
2.5.1 Description.....	39
2.5.2 Data summary for WP5.....	40
2.5.3 To whom the data might be useful.....	41
2.5.4 Possibility of integration and re-use	41

2.6	WP6: Project Coordination and Management.....	41
2.6.1	Description.....	41
2.6.2	Data summary for WP6.....	42
2.6.3	To whom the data might be useful.....	43
2.6.4	Possibility of integration and re-use	43
3	FAIR data.....	44
3.1	Criteria for FAIR data	45
3.2	WP1 FAIR data.....	46
3.2.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	46
3.2.2	Making data accessible.....	46
3.2.3	Making data interoperable.....	46
3.2.4	Increase data re-use.....	47
3.3	WP2 FAIR data.....	47
3.3.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	47
3.3.2	Making data accessible.....	48
3.3.3	Making data interoperable.....	49
3.3.4	Increase data re-use.....	49
3.4	WP3 FAIR data.....	50
3.4.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	50
3.4.2	Making data accessible.....	50
3.4.3	Making data interoperable.....	51
3.4.4	Increase data re-use.....	51
3.5	WP4 FAIR data.....	51
3.5.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	51
3.5.2	Making data accessible.....	52
3.5.3	Making data interoperable.....	52
3.5.4	Increase data re-use.....	53
3.6	WP5 FAIR data.....	53
3.6.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	53
3.6.2	Making data accessible.....	53
3.6.3	Making data interoperable.....	54
3.6.4	Increase data re-use.....	54
3.7	WP6 FAIR data.....	54
3.7.1	Making data findable, including provisions for metadata.....	54
3.7.2	Making data accessible.....	55
3.7.3	Making data interoperable.....	55
3.7.4	Increase data re-use.....	55
4	Other research outputs.....	56
4.1	Research outputs besides data.....	56
4.2	FAIR management of research outputs.....	56

4.3	Open access to research outputs.....	57
5	Allocation of resources.....	58
5.1	Costs for FAIR data and research.....	58
5.2	Data management responsibilities.....	58
6	Data security.....	61
6.1	Provisions for data security	61
6.2	Data protection regulations.....	62
6.2.1	GDPR.....	62
6.2.2	Country specific regulations	63
6.3	Third parties	63
7	Ethics.....	65
7.1	Ethical governance procedures.....	65
7.2	Ethical considerations.....	65
7.3	Informed consent and personal data.....	66
7.3.1	Informed consent.....	66
7.3.2	Personal data	67
7.4	Human participation	68
7.4.1	Indigenous and traditional knowledge	68
7.4.2	Vulnerable groups	69
7.5	Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning	70
7.5.1	Time-lapse cameras	71
7.5.2	Drones	72
7.5.3	Impacts on using drones and time-lapse cameras.....	73
7.6	Organic and inorganic samples.....	74
7.6.1	Sediment sampling.....	74
7.6.2	Food samples.....	74
7.6.3	Toxicological impact analysis of micro- and nano-plastics and other contaminants (PFAS) on human digestive health.....	75
7.6.4	Impacts of working with organic and inorganic samples	75
8	References.....	77
9	Appendices.....	78
9.1	Appendix 1: Data questionnaire for partners.....	78
9.2	Appendix 2: Information Form.....	83
9.3	Appendix 3: Written Consent Form.....	84
9.4	Appendix 4: Written Consent Form for Youth	85

List of Tables

Table 1. Data summary for WP1	11
Table 2. Data summary for WP2	16
Table 3. Data summary for WP3	29
Table 4. Data summary for WP4	33
Table 5. Data summary for WP5	40
Table 6. Data summary for WP6	42
Table 7. Questions asked to determine how the data complies with each FAIR category	45
Table 8. Roles and responsibilities for data management in the ICEBERG project	59
Table 9. Third parties who handle data from the ICEBERG project	63
Table 10. Potential risks to vulnerable groups and how to mitigate them.	69
Table 11. Potential negative impact of use and handline drones, time-lapse cameras and how to minimize.....	73
Table 12. Potential risk to local environment/ecosystem and humans and how to mitigate the risks	76

Acronyms and Abbreviations

AI	Artificial Intelligence
ALTAI	Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
ASTD	Arctic Ship Traffic Data
BBNJ	United Nations agreement on biodiversity beyond national jurisdiction
CARE	Collective benefit, authority to control, responsibility, ethics
CBEM	Community-based Environmental Monitoring
CC BY 4.0	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International
CMLO	Coastal Marine Litter Observatory
CRM	Certified Reference Materials
DECO	Dissemination, Exploitation, Communication and Outreach
DEI	Diverse, Equitable, and Inclusive
DESCA	Development of a Simplified Consortium Agreement
DFG	German Research Foundation (Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft)
DMP	Data Management Plan
DMS	Dimethyl sulfide
DoA	Description of the Action
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
Dx.x	Deliverable number
EASA	European Union Aviation Safety Agency
EMP	Ethics Management Plan
EOM	Earth Observation and Modelling
ESA	European Space Agency
EU	European Union

EU GA	EU Grant Agreement
EU-PolarNet	Integrated European Polar Research Programme
FAIR	Findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable
FPIC	Free prior informed consent
GCHR	Greenland's Centre for Health Research
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
HTTPS	Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure
IASSA	International Arctic Social Sciences Association
ICC	Inuit Circumpolar Council
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
MPA	Marine Protected Area
MS Teams	Microsoft Teams
Mx	Month number
NGO	Non-governmental organization
ODbL	Open Data Commons Open Database License
PAH	Polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons
PFAS	Per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances
PMG	Project Management Group
QA/QC	Quality Assurance/Quality Control
QAP	Quality Assurance Plan
RDM	Research data management
RiS	Research in Svalbard
SFTP	Secure File Transfer Protocol
SIOS	Svalbard Integrated Arctic Earth Observing System

SSRN	Social Science Research Network
UNCLOS	United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea
UNDRIP	United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
WPx	Work package number
.ai	Adobe Illustrator file
.avi	Audio Video Interleave video file
.csv	Comma-separated values
.doc, .docx	Microsoft Word document
.indd	Adobe InDesign document
.jpg, .jpeg	JPEG image file
.mat	MATLAB data file
.mov	QuickTime movie file
.mp3	MP3 audio file
.mp4	MPEG-4 video file
.nc	NetCDF file
.pdf	Portable Document Format
.png	Portable Network Graphics image file
.ppt, .pptx	Microsoft PowerPoint presentation
.pzfx	Prism project file
.shp	Shapefile
.tif	Tagged Image File Format (e.g. GeoTIFF)
.txt	Text file
.xls, .xlsx	Excel spreadsheet

1 Introduction

1.1 Scope

This document is the Mid-term Data Management Plan (DMP) of the ICEBERG project (project number 101135130), which is established by month 18 (M18) of the project. This DMP follows the template recommended for Horizon Europe beneficiaries and addresses the requirements for research data management of Horizon Europe as described in Article 17 (section: Open Science) of Annex 5 in the Grant Agreement (EU GA). This deliverable (D6.4) represents the second version of the DMP, which will be followed by the Final Data Management Plan (D6.5) in M36. It is also associated with the D6.3 Ethics Management Plan. This document represents the current state of the DMP and supersedes the previous document, D6.2 First Data Management Plan. Specific changes to the previous version are as follows:

- updates on data summary tables 1, 2, 3 and 4
- minor changes in the FAIR data section
- updates on Ethics section
- addition of Information Sheet and Consent form in Appendix section.

1.2 Purpose

The purpose of the Mid-term DMP is to update and revise the data management life cycle of all data sets that is collected, processed or generated by the ICEBERG project. This plan covers the entire data management life cycle and identifies the datasets and their descriptions, as well as how the research data will be handled and preserved after the completion of the project. The Mid-term DMP will adhere to the Open Science Approach and Research Data Management principles. The Mid-term DMP also addresses ethical concerns related to personal data, Indigenous knowledge, biological samples, and artificial intelligence (AI) that arise during the project's life cycle.

1.3 DMP Methodology

The Mid-term DMP was developed under the Task 6.4 Data management and ethics led by the ICEBERG project's coordination team (UOULU). The First DMP (D6.2) was collaboratively developed by UFZ and UOULU and collected data from all partners regarding data management and ethics (see questions in Appendix 1). This document revises and updates all responses compiled and outlined in this plan. The Mid-term DMP establishes best practices and relevant standards as a quality assurance for the data collected and generated in the ICEBERG project.

2 Data Summary

The ICEBERG data is presented by work packages (WPs), listed below along with the data types that the WPs *mainly* produce or use:

- WP1: in-situ environmental data, model outputs, visual media (e.g. time-lapse images)
- WP2: in-situ environmental data, interviews/focus groups, surveys, visual media (e.g. film, photo voice, drone images)
- WP3: interviews, regulations/legislation information
- WP4: interviews/focus groups, surveys, consortium co-creation data
- WP5: stakeholder information, contact information, visual media (e.g. posters)
- WP6: consortium co-creation data

The DMP defines and establishes consistent practices among project partners in regard to methods within and across work packages. The intention is to increase the efficiency of data handling during the project and increase the quality of research by defining institutional and project-specific data management policies and plans in accordance with relevant standards and community best practice.

2.1 WP1: Assessment of pollution sources, distribution, and impacts in Arctic ecosystems

2.1.1 Description

This work package aims to advance the scientific understanding of the sources, distributions, and impacts of pollution across the land-ocean continuum on ecosystem services in the European Arctic. In order to achieve this, the WP will develop model simulations that are complemented by data from remote sensing, as well as in-situ observations and laboratory measurements.

The data generated and used by WP1 is summarised in the next section.

2.1.2 Data summary for WP1

Table 1. Data summary for WP1

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
Model results with pathways and impact of pollutants in seawater	Identify and trace pollution's potential impacts as well as their temporal and spatial distribution in the European Arctic	1.1	.xlsx, .mat, .txt, .nc	Uses: Primary data from ICEBERG study sites, Hausgarten (Fram Strait); Secondary data from Arctic Ship Traffic Data (ASTD) Generates: Primary data in form of model results and data –model syntheses	approx. 2 TB (for subsets of model results)	Open access (prior to publication and/or deliverable report only for ICEBERG consortia members; hereafter, openly accessible)	Researcher hard drives, GEOMAR cloud, OSIS, (GEOMAR data repository)
Omics molecular data	Identifying, describing and quantifying the structure, the genetic potential and functional gene expression of the Arctic Ocean Plastisphere Resistome	1.2	.xlsx, .fastq	Primary data from ICEBERG study sites, Hausgarten (Fram Strait) Generates: Summary table of antibiotic resistance genes and relative abundance.	1000 GB	Open access (deliverables upon completion, raw data upon publication)	Researcher hard drives, GEOMAR cloud, OSIS (GEOMAR data repository), European Nucleotide Archive (ENA)
Quantitative organic pollutant concentrations in sediment, snow and ice	Understand the land-ocean transfer of frozen-lock pollutants and provide a historical perspective on the	1.3	.xlsx, .tif, geotiff	Primary data collected in the field; Secondary data from existing literature	20 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, CNR network drive

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
	atmospheric and oceanic sources of pollutants						
Quantitative microplastic concentrations in sediment, snow and zooplankton	Assess the transfer of microplastic in zooplankton	1.3	.xlsx, .tif,	Primary data collected in the field; Secondary data from existing literature	20 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, CNR network drive
Quantification of pollution types and amounts (e.g. concentration of PAH, number of microplastic particles) in seawater	Measure different types of pollution, generate data for modelling	1.6	.xlsx, .mat, .txt	Primary data from ICEBERG study sites, Hausgarten (Fram Strait)	5 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, GEOMAR cloud, OSIS (GEOMAR data repository)
Quantification of changes in biological parameters and biogenic gases in seawater due to presence of pollution (e.g. DMS)	Measure different types of pollution, generate data for modelling	1.7	.xlsx, .mat, .txt	Primary data from ICEBERG study sites, Hausgarten (Fram Strait)	5 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, GEOMAR cloud, OSIS (GEOMAR data repository)

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
concentrations, cell counts)							
Quantitative, qualitative and distributional data on stranded marine litter	Obtain data regarding plastic pollution in the near-shore-open ocean terrestrial environment (the littoral zone) of the Arctic to assess remote sources/anthropogenic and impacts/exchange	1.8	.xlsx, .csv	Primary data collected from South-western Sørkappland (Andvika to Breineset), Svalbard; Secondary data generated under Sørkapp Marine Litter Cleanup	20 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, online drive, POLAR-PL
Quantitative, qualitative and distributional data on marine litter accumulation rate	Obtain data regarding plastic pollution in the near-shore-open ocean terrestrial environment (the littoral zone) of the Arctic to assess remote sources/anthropogenic and impacts/exchange	1.8	.xlsx, .csv	Primary data collected in the field from South-western Sørkappland (Andvika to Breineset), Svalbard; Secondary data generated under Sørkapp Marine Litter Cleanup	20 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, online drive, POLAR-PL
Image data collected from tripod-based time lapse camera at a pre-defined interval	Continuous monitoring of the litter dynamics through one camera overlooking a single section of a single beach in southern Spitsbergen for a period of one year	1.9	.jpg	Primary data directly generated by the time-lapse camera	5 TB	Open access	EOM (Earth Observation and Modeling working group) network drive, CAU Cloud

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
Quantitative and qualitative data on chemical composition of freshwater and snow: a) anions, b) cations, c) alkalinity, d) metals (including heavy metals)	Report on impacts of pollution in the European Arctic	1.10	.xlsx, .csv, .pdf	Primary data collected in the field from South-western Sørkappland (Andvika to Breineset), Southern Svalbard; area around Longyearbyen, Central Svalbard	20 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, Analytical Chemistry Department of the Adam Mickiewicz University of Poznań network drive (spectrometry analysis data), POLAR-PL
Quantitative and qualitative data on chemical composition of soils (including heavy metals)	Report on impacts of pollution in the European Arctic	1.10	.xlsx, .csv, .pdf	Primary data collected in the field from South-western Sørkappland (Andvika to Breineset), Southern Svalbard; area around Longyearbyen, Central Svalbard; Secondary data generated by the forScience Foundation in previous years	20 MB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, Analytical Chemistry Department of the Adam Mickiewicz University of Poznań network drive (spectrometry analysis data), POLAR-PL

2.1.3 To whom the data might be useful

The data may be useful for the following groups outside the project:

- Researchers writing review papers on Arctic pollution or comparing/tracking changes of Arctic pollution,
- Researchers using time series datasets over remote areas (such datasets are rare and usually not available to the research community),
- Communities who rely on the environment for their livelihoods and traditional practices may use this data to understand the potential impacts of pollution on their way of life.

Working groups addressing Arctic pollution are committed to delivering informed, science-based evaluations and effective public communication tools to guide policy development and decision-making.

2.1.4 Possibility of integration and re-use

The data from WP1 can be used for further publications, proposal applications, and comparison purposes, based on results already published with the agreement of the partners. Data from quantification of pollution, changes in biological parameters due to pollution, and model results may be re-used by partners when writing review papers, inter-comparison studies, and for tracking changes in the future.

2.2 WP2: Risk assessment and local resilience strategies for ecosystems and communities in response to pollution

2.2.1 Description

The aims of this work package are to assess the impact of pollution and climate change on coastal and marine ecosystems and food webs, and their effects on local communities; as well as to provide data that will inform policies and decision-making processes that will help mitigate the impacts of pollution and climate change on coastal and marine ecosystems, food webs, and local communities. To achieve this, the WP will analyse changes observed by locals, use satellite and airborne tracking to monitor infrastructure development, co-develop strategies for adaptation with local communities, and establish long-term community-based environmental monitoring systems.

The data generated and used by WP2 is summarised in the next section.

2.2.2 Data summary for WP2

Table 2. Data summary for WP2

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
Interview recordings and notes (with community)	To understand locally observed pollution and environmental changes, their perceived impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems, and to co-develop adaptation strategies with local communities	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	.mp4, .mp3	Primary data collected from communities during interviews in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Nanortalik, Narsarsuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, UOULU/SAI/ ULAP network drives, MS Teams, Dropbox
Interview transcripts and notes (with community)	To understand locally observed pollution and environmental changes, their perceived impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems, and to co-develop adaptation strategies with local communities	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	.docx, .txt, hand-written	Primary data collected from communities during interviews in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Nanortalik, Narsarsuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	50 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, UOULU/SAI/ ULAP network drives, MS Teams, Dropbox
Focus group recordings and notes (with community)	To understand locally observed pollution and environmental changes, their perceived impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems, and to co-develop adaptation	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	.mp4, .mp3	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Nanortalik, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, UOULU/SAI/ ULAP network drives, MS Teams, Dropbox

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
	strategies with local communities						
Focus group notes (with community)	To understand locally observed pollution and environmental changes, their perceived impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems, and to co-develop adaptation strategies with local communities	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	.docx, .txt, hand-written	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland)	50 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, UOULU/SAI/ ULAP network drives, MS Teams, Dropbox
Field notes	To understand locally observed pollution and environmental changes, their perceived impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems, and to co-develop adaptation strategies with local communities	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	Hand-written, .doc	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsarsuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland)	20 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, university and institution network drives
CBEM Survey submissions (text)	To understand the locally observed changes related to pollution and environmental change, as well as the perceptions and experiences of local communities regarding	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	.xls, .xlsx, .csv	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsarsuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland); Primary data collected by researchers in Ny-Ålesund	50 MB	Open access (except optional contact details)	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, researcher hard drives, UFZ/UOULU network drives, LimeSurvey (third

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
	these changes and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; and to provide data for the CBEM platform			(Svalbard) for testing the CBEM platform			party survey host), uMap (third part interactive mapping platform), local curator hard drive (the community member who quality checks and uploads the data)
CBEM Survey submissions (images)	To understand the observed changes related to pollution and environmental change, as well as the perceptions and experiences of local communities regarding these changes and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; and to provide data for the CBEM platform	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	.png, .jpg	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland); Primary data collected by researchers in Ny-Ålesund (Svalbard) for testing the CBEM platform	5 GB	Open access	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, researcher hard drives, UFZ/UOULU network drives, LimeSurvey (third party survey host), uMap (third part interactive mapping platform), local curator hard drive (the community member who quality checks and uploads the data)

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
CBEM Survey submissions (personal data)	To collect optional contact details from survey users if they want to be contacted for more information; To enhance two-way interaction and foster community between citizens and researchers	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	.xls, .xlsx, .csv	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Narsasuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	20 MB	Not open access	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, researcher hard drives, UFZ/UOULU network drives, LimeSurvey (third party survey host), local curator hard drive (the community member who quality checks and uploads the data)
Arctic tourism Survey submissions (text)	Survey data to understand the perceptions of cruise and land-based tourists on Arctic environment and sustainable tourism	2.1, 2.3	.xlsx, .pdf, .docx.	Primary data collected from cruise ship tourists and land-based tourists in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Narsasuaq, (Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland);	5 MB	Not open access	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, researcher hard drives, UOULU/ULAP/SAI/CAU network drives, Webropol (third party survey host)
Arctic tourism Survey submissions (personal data)	To collect details related to demographical background of respondents	2.1, 2.3	.xlsx, .pdf, docx	Primary data collected from cruise ship tourists and land-based tourists in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and	500 KB	Not open access	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, researcher hard drives, UOULU/ULAP/SAI/

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
				Qaqortoq,, Narsarsuaq, (Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland);			CAU network drives, Webropol (third party survey host)
Cartographic data (for CBEM platform)	To understand the locally observed changes related to pollution and environmental change, as well as the perceptions and experiences of local communities regarding these changes and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; and to provide data visualisations for the CBEM platform	2.10	.shp, .png, .jpg <u>.txt</u> <u>.mov</u>	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsaq Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland)	5 GB	Open access	uMap (third party interactive mapping platform), OVHcloud (uMap servers)
Cartographic data (paper maps)	To understand locally observed pollution and environmental changes, their perceived impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To provide an alternative (offline) method for citizens to share geographic data	2.1, 2.3, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	Paper, .jpg	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Nanortalik, Narsarsuaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland)	5 GB	Open access (with consent from community members)	Researcher hard drives, UOULU/SAI/ ULAP network drives

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
Photographs from photovoice project	To understand locally observed pollution and environmental changes, their perceived impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems; To provide a creative, participatory method for citizens to share their perceptions, emotions and experiences.	2.1, 2.3, 2.7, 2.8	.jpg, .png	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsaq Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	1 TB	Open access (with consent from photographer)	Researcher hard drives, university and institute network drives, personal hard drive of citizen photographer
Photo contest submissions (images)	Photos to provide data for CBEM platform and for use in uMap capacity building community workshop. To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems. Participants are invited to submit a photo that captures either an environmental success story (such as a clean-up or community initiative), a	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	.png, .jpg	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Nanortalik (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	5 GB	Open access (with consent of photographer)	Researcher hard drives, university and institute network drives (UOULU, UFZ), personal hard drive of citizen photographer, ICEBERG website, uMap (third party interactive mapping platform; servers: OVHcloud), WebRoPol (third party survey host)

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
	place they are helping to protect or restore, or a polluted site accompanied by their vision of what the place should look like						
Photo contest submissions (text)	Text (accompanying the photo submissions, above) to provide data for CBEM platform and for use in uMap capacity building community workshop. To understand the perceptions and experiences of local communities observed changes regarding pollution, and their impacts on livelihoods and ecosystems.	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	(Depends on how they submit. Tbd)	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsaq (Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland)	50 MB	Open access (with consent of photographer)	Researcher hard drives, university and institute network drives, personal hard drive of citizen photographer, ICEBERG website, uMap (third party interactive mapping platform; servers: OVHcloud), WebRoPol (third party survey host)
Photo contest submission (personal data)	To collect contact details from contest entries so they can be contacted about the workshop/prize-giving; To enhance two-way interaction and foster	2.1, 2.2, 2.3, 2.5, 2.7, 2.8, 2.9, 2.10	.txt	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Nanortalik, Narsaq, (Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland)	20 MB	Not open access (only used by researchers to contact contest entrants)	Researcher hard drives, university and institute network drives, WebRoPol (third party survey host)

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
	community between citizens and researchers						
Photographs from airborne drone images	To map and monitor marine litter concentrations; To provide images for processing with machine learning algorithms to produce marine litter density maps of study areas	2.1	.jpg	Primary data collected by airborne drone mapping from 2-4 coastal sites in Iceland and Greenland	5 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, SCI network drive, ICEBERG Onedrive, Coastal Marine Litter Observatory (CMLO) platform
Image data collected from tripod-based time lapse cameras at a pre-defined interval	For continuous monitoring of the litter dynamics through tower-based cameras overlooking a section of the test beaches	2.1.1	.jpg	Primary data directly generated by the time-lapse cameras	5 TB	Not open access	EOM (Earth Observation and Modelling working group) network drive, CAU Cloud
Marine litter density maps	To map and monitor marine litter concentrations	2.1	.pdf	Primary data generated from images collected by airborne drone mapping from 2-4 coastal sites in Iceland and Greenland	50 MB	Open access	Researcher hard drive, SCI network drive, ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, Coastal Marine Litter Observatory (CMLO) platform

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
Quantitative data on contamination by various chemical pollutants, i.e. concentrations	Generate analytical data to characterise the occurrence of chemical contaminants in various compartments (environment, food, human), in order to study exposure of the population of Greenland and Iceland to chemical contaminants via their diet	2.2, 2.4	.xlsx	Primary data generated within the laboratory	1 TB	Open access	Researcher hard drive, ONIRIS network drive
Quantitative datasets from standardised bioassays (e.g. ELISA, RT-PCR, kits for evaluating cytotoxicity, genotoxicity, oxidative stress)	Toxicological assessment of nano-plastics and other contaminants (e.g. PFAS) on human digestive health	2.2, 2.4	.xlsx, .pzfx	Primary data generated within the laboratory	1 TB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, INRAE network drive
Quantitative and qualitative data on stranded marine litter collected during beach clean-ups	Obtain data regarding plastic pollution in the fjord environment in North Iceland to assess remote sources/anthropogenic influences and their	2.4	.xlsx	Primary data generated in the Eyjafjörður (Akureyri, Iceland) in collaboration with Ocean Missions' beach clean-ups	5 GB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, INRAE network drive

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
	impacts/exchange in these coastal waters						
Quantitative data on the physico-chemical characteristics of nanoplastics (e.g. FTIR spectra, DLS for size distribution, TGA, Py-GCMS, Microscopy images)	Synthesize and characterize environmentally relevant nanoplastics for toxicological testing	2.4	.xlsx .jpg .tif	Primary data generated within the laboratory	1 TB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, INRAE network drive
Observation-based data from CMIP6 decadal predictions	To provide climate-related information for the project WPs and for co-development of climate services with Arctic stakeholders	2.5	.nc, .csv	Secondary data from public repositories with meteorological station data and model outputs	1 TB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, BSC network drive
Climate-related indicators	To provide climate-related information for the project WPs and for co-development of climate services with Arctic stakeholders	2.5	.nc, .csv	Secondary data reusing existing data generated by BSC	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, BSC network drive

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
Data on international legal instruments and customary law	To gather information on policy, regulation and legislation covering pollutants in order to provide a synthesis and assessment of existing governance and management approaches; To examine their value for the co-creation of novel/complementary governance approaches under the application of the One Health approach	2.9	.pdf	Secondary data reusing publicly available information and data on international legal instruments e.g. (e.g., UNCLOS, BBNJ, UNDRIP, High Seas Treaty, Plastic Pollution Treaty) and customary law	50 MB	Open access	Researcher hard drives, ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams
Database of regulations	To provide data for WP3 regarding decision-making processes and policies; To identify related legal response measures (e.g. new MPAs) building on international legal instruments and customary law	2.9	Online database	Secondary data from legal and policy databases, national and EU databases (EUR-Lex), UN treaty database	50 MB	Open access	Researcher hard drive, WaveLinks database
Dietary habit survey (responses)	To understand the dietary habits of local populations in Iceland and Greenland, to select the most relevant	2.2	.xlsx	Responses collected electronically via online survey (advertised in Facebook for two months).	20 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, institution network drives

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
	food matrices for chemical analysis						
Notes and recordings from focus groups with women	To understand observations of environmental change and pollution by women, as well its impacts on them. To gather insights related to food (procurement, preparation, consumption), well-being, identity, and any public health guidelines	2.1, 2.3, 2.4	.mp3 .mp4 .docx .pdf	Primary data collected from communities in Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Narsaq (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	2 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive

2.2.3 To whom the data might be useful

The data may be useful for the following groups outside the project:

- Researchers, for example in social science and humanities working on Arctic pollution or governance,
- Researchers working on marine and coastal dynamics can access marine litter density maps on the Coastal Marine Litter Observatory (CMLO) platform and use them to improve the detection and mapping of marine litter in the coastal zone,
- Interested community members who want a visualisation of pollution and to monitor their local environments long-term (CBEM data),
- Public health authorities may use the data to improve health related strategies,
- Management authorities, municipalities and conservation authorities at the local level can use the data to inform land use planning, climate change adaptation and mitigation plans, and for pollution control,
- Management authorities and decision makers for EU Arctic policy can use the database of regulations to allow for easy compilation and review of regulations applicable to different pollutants within each jurisdiction,
- Educators using drone/time-lapse image datasets for teaching beach and litter dynamics.

2.2.4 Possibility of integration and re-use

Data generated by WP2 may be used as a case study for future publications or research outputs. Quantitative data (e.g. pollutants, plastics, contaminants) may be re-used for comparison purposes for future studies. Interview data from community members will be re-used only if prior consent for this is established. These data can be used for comparison studies in the future of long-term interviews series, and with other Arctic projects and sites. The database of regulations allows for easy re-use of data through compilations and reviews of regulations applicable to different pollutants within each jurisdiction. This would facilitate future Arctic pollution governance research as well as research on global frameworks. Media (photos, videos, paper maps, photovoice entries) may be re-used as visual aids for non-commercial, pedagogical and scientific purposes. Further, the videos may be re-used for film screenings, schools, and conferences (for non-commercial purposes). Drone images will be re-used to retrain machine learning algorithms for detecting marine litter in the Arctic environment. In addition, since collection of drone and time-lapse camera image data and upkeep of the time lapse cameras and the drones involve local communities/schools in Iceland and Greenland, insights from this data may be re-used for teaching purposes by the partners or the communities.

2.3 WP3: Facilitating effective science-based pollution-control governance

2.3.1 Description

This work package aims to support and strengthen the implementation of the EU Arctic policy, 3rd Arctic Science Ministerial meeting and the work of the Arctic Council in regard to the effective prevention and mitigation of pollution in the Arctic. In order to achieve this, the WP will examine the existing governance approaches and their challenges and shortcomings for providing specifically tailored novel policy recommendations. Data generated by this work package will contribute to an understanding of the science-policy nexus (WP1) and strengthen the application of a truly holistic approach (WP2).

The data generated and used by WP3 is summarised in the next section.

2.2.4 Data summary for WP3

Table 3. Data summary for WP3

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
Interview recordings (with national and international policy-makers)	To provide data for WP3 regarding decision-making processes and policies	3.1, 3.2, 3.3	.mp3	Primary data collected during interviews with decision-makers and experts at the national level (not community members) in Iceland and Greenland (national agencies and ministries)	33 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, ULAP network drives
Interview transcripts (with national and international policy-makers)	To provide data for WP3 regarding decision-making processes and policies	3.1, 3.2, 3.3	.docx	Primary data collected during interviews with decision-makers and experts at a supra-local level (not community members) in Iceland, and Greenland	1.5 MB Over 12000 words	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, ULAP network drives, Dropbox
Interview recordings (with case study region political and industry stakeholders)	To gather insights on the local perspectives (national and subnational political level) of existing governance gaps and developments with regard to pollution control	3.1	.mp4	Primary data collected during interviews with political actors, authorities and further societal stakeholders in Iceland	601 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, Secure ULAP Cloud
Interview transcripts (with case study region political and industry stakeholders)	To gather insights on the local perspectives (national and subnational political level) of existing governance gaps with stakeholders	3.1	.docx	Primary data collected during interviews with political actors, authorities and further societal stakeholders in Iceland (March 2025 fieldwork) and Greenland (Greenland – governance-relevant notes from	20 MB Over 60000 words	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, Secure ULAP cloud

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
	regard to pollution control			interviews and meetings during 2024 fieldwork)			
Interview recordings (with case study region stakeholders with focus on gender questions)	To gather insights for the analysis and identification of gaps and opportunities for the integration of a gender-dimension of pollution in the case study regions	3.4	.mp3, .mp4, .mov, .avi	Primary data collected during interviews with community members of women's associations in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland); Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Nuuk (Greenland). May be part of the interviews conducted primarily for other tasks and WPs.	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams
Interview transcripts (with case study region stakeholders with focus on gender questions)	To gather insights for the analysis and identification of gaps and opportunities for the integration of a gender-dimension of pollution in the case study regions	3.4	.docx, .xlsx, .pdf	Primary data collected during interviews with community members of women's associations in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland); Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Nuuk (Greenland). May be part of the interviews conducted primarily for other tasks and WPs.	20 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams
Data on local, national, regional and international marine pollutants governance	To gather information on policy, regulation and legislation covering pollutants in order to provide a synthesis and assessment of existing governance and management approaches; To examine their value for	3.1, 3.2, 3.3, 3.4	.pdf	Secondary data reusing publicly available information on local, national, regional and international data on Marine pollutants governance	20 MB	Under development, eventually Open access in the form of a database and policy papers	Researcher hard drives, ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
	the co-creation of novel/complementary governance approaches under the application of the One Health approach						
Notes and recordings from focus groups with women	To understand observations of environmental change and pollution by women, as well its impacts on them. To gather insights related public health guidelines and governance.	3.4	.mp3 .mp4 .docx .pdf hand-written	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri & Húsavík (Iceland)	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive

2.3.3 To whom the data might be useful

The data may be useful for the following groups outside the project:

- Researchers in Arctic governance would be interested in the novel data from political stakeholders,
- Management and public authorities and decision makers for EU Arctic policy,
- Crucial actors (e.g. environmental organizations and NGOs) working on pollution prevention and mitigation in the Arctic.

2.3.4 Possibility of integration and re-use

Data generated by WP3 may be re-used for further publications and future governance comparison research. Interview data will be re-used only if prior consent for this is established. Interview data from decision-makers can be used to compare insights from Greenland, Iceland and Svalbard with future insights obtained from decision-makers in other Arctic regions, focusing on environmental governance, management and the One Health approach. Data on regulations will be included in the regulatory and policy database, as well as in the internal policy papers finalized by project month 17. These would be designed to be part of cross-project integration and reuse by other researchers.

2.4 WP4: Co-Creation, Ethics, Diversity, Equity and Inclusion

2.4.1 Description

This work package develops: an overarching framework that ensures research adherence to co-creation, ethics, diversity, equity, and inclusion in all WPs; as well as a Diverse, Equitable, and Inclusive (DEI) research code of conduct and ethical standards for co-creation, data management, and knowledge dissemination. In order to achieve this, the WP supports the co-production and coordination of methodologies across WPs, provides all WPs with recommendations on co-creation, develops guidelines for engaging with Indigenous partners and amplifies existing protocols for community-based research. This WP also co-creates monitoring and evaluation criteria for the project in collaboration with local communities.

The data generated and used by WP4 is summarised in the next section.

2.3.2 Data summary for WP4

Table 4. Data summary for WP4

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
Consortium External Stakeholder Analysis notes	To identify stakeholders the project intends to involve in co-production processes	4.1	Online (Miro Board), .pdf	Primary data generated during internal online workshops with consortium members and at GA meetings	N/A	Open access (screenshots in public level reports)	Miro Board (initial stakeholder mapping) Teams shared WP4 folder and researchers hard drive (subsequent updates to the stakeholder mapping after fieldwork)
Consortium Flow of Information Timeline notes	To identify points of interdependencies and collaboration in terms of data collection and co-production	4.1	Online (Miro Board), .jpg	Primary data generated during internal online workshops with consortium members	N/A	Open access (screenshots in public level reports)	Miro Board
Consortium reading group notes	To generate insights for the ICEBERG project based on consortium co-creation in ethics; To provide a shared space across disciplines and WPs to reflect on project ethics	4.2	Online (Miro Board)	Primary data generated during internal online reading group meetings with consortium members	N/A	Not open access	Miro Board

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
Empathy maps (with consortium)	To provide initial feedback about the CBEM platform from a user's perspective ahead of public release and at community consultation meetings	4.5	.pptx, .jpg	Primary data generated during internal online workshop with consortium members	50 MB	Open access (screenshots in public level reports)	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, researcher hard drive, UFZ network drive
Interview recordings (with community)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with communities	4.2, 4.4	.mp4, .mp3	Primary data collected from communities during interviews in Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland)	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive
Interview transcripts (with community)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with communities	4.2, 4.4	.docx	Primary data collected from communities during interviews in Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland)	50 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive
Interview recordings (with consortium)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and	4.2	.mp4, .mp3	Primary data collected from online and in-person meetings with consortium members	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
	give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with consortium						
Interview transcripts (with consortium)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with consortium	4.2	.docx	Primary data collected from online and in-person meetings with consortium members	20 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive
Focus group recordings (with consortium)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with consortium	4.2	.mp4, .mp3	Primary data collected from online and in-person meetings with consortium members	1 TB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive
Focus group notes (with consortium)	To ensure assessment criteria and methods are culturally appropriate and	4.2	.docx, hand-written,	Primary data collected from online and in-person meetings with consortium members	20 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drive, GFZ network drive, Miro Board

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
	give justice to the situatedness of knowledges and expertise; To co-develop ethics evaluation framework with consortium		online (Miro Board)				
Field notes	To co-create strategies with local communities in the dimensions of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI), gender, and ethics	4.2, 4.3, 4.4, 4.5	Hand-written, .docx	Primary data collected from communities in Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	50 MB	Not open access	Researcher hard drives, GFZ & UFZ network drive, WoA hard drive
Photographs and video taken by researchers	To document every phase of the project, especially during fieldwork in Iceland and Greenland, during the consortium meetings and the preparation phase of these meetings	4.2, 4.4, 4.5	.jpg, .mp4, .mov	Primary data collected from case study sites Akureyri and Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Narsaq, Nuuk (Kalaallit Nunaat-Greenland)	1 TB	Open access with consent of photographer and persons in photos	Researcher hard drives/devices, GFZ & UFZ network drive, WoA hard drive
Survey submissions (from consortium)	To co-create strategies and guidelines with the consortium in the dimensions of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI), gender, and ethics	4.1, 4.2, 4.3, 4.4	.xls, .xlsx, .csv, online	Primary data collected from consortium members using various online survey platforms	20 MB	Not open access	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams, researcher hard drives, university or institute network drives, Mentimeter (third party presentation-based)

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
							digital tool), Webropol (third party survey platform)
Notes and recordings from focus groups with women	To understand observations of environmental change and pollution by women, as well its impacts on them. To gather insights related to gender equality, food (procurement, preparation, consumption), well-being, identity, and any public health guidelines	4.4	.mp3 .mp4 docx .pdf hand-written	Primary data collected from communities in Húsavík (Iceland) and Qaqortoq, Narsaq (Kalaallit Nunaat- Greenland)	2 TB	Not open access	WoA hard drive
Consortium Retrospective Workshop	Meeting of WP leads to identify what worked for their WPs and what did not	4.3	Online (Miro Board)	Primary data generated during internal online workshops with consortium members	N/A	Not open access	Miro Board
Parenting & Fieldwork Survey Submissions	To gather insights on the challenges and strategies employed by parents in the field (both apart from children and during accompanied fieldwork); to inform strategies for enhancing support	4.4, 4.5	.xls, .xlsx, .csv	Primary data collected from consenting researchers around the world (any discipline/gender) who have conducted fieldwork while in a parental role, either currently or in the past	1 GB	Not open access	ICEBERG OneDrive, researcher hard drives, UFZ/WoA network drives, LimeSurvey (third party survey host)

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
	systems and resources for parents in field-based research						
Transcripts of sticky notes from GA sessions, meetings, minutes & reports	To assess living CoC and co-evaluation process of research ethics and identify best-practices	4.2, 4.4	.txt, .docx, .pdf	Primary data collected during project workshop, online meetings of or in person during the GA's	1GB	Not open access	GFZ institute network drive, WoA hard drive

2.4.3 To whom the data might be useful

The data may be useful for the following groups outside the project:

- Other projects generating guidelines in the dimensions of diversity, equity, and inclusion (DEI), gender, and ethics,
- Researchers and projects working closely with local communities e.g. co-creating strategies and frameworks,
- Researchers and projects looking for alternative ethnographic methods of co-creation and reflection.

2.4.4 Possibility of integration and re-use

Much of the data in WP4 is generated internally and intended to be used as insights when co-creating guidelines and frameworks relating to the project. Thus, the data may be continuously re-used throughout the project life cycle to update “living documents” (e.g. ICEBERG Code of Conduct). Interview data collected from communities may be used in future comparison studies with other projects/sites, which will be explicitly explained in consent forms.

2.5 WP5: Communication, Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach

2.5.1 Description

This work package is responsible for handling the Communication, Dissemination, and Exploitation of results to maximize project outreach and facilitate dialogue with relevant stakeholders (e.g. Indigenous communities, local communities, civil society organizations, policy and decision makers, financial institutions, and environmental managers). In order to achieve this, the WP: uses a co-design approach in designing inclusive science communication activities together with the project partners and stakeholders; promotes the project and progress with targeted communication activities to relevant stakeholders and wider society; and increases exchange of information between the project and its stakeholders.

The data generated and used by WP5 is summarised in the next section.

2.3.4 Data summary for WP5

Table 5. Data summary for WP5

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
Stakeholder database for email lists	To communicate the progress and outcomes of the project via newsletters	5.1	.xlsx	Primary data collected from the ICEBERG website newsletter sign-up form	20 MB	Not open access	Project directory in Mailchimp
Stakeholder database for events	To communicate the progress and outcomes of the project through events	5.2	.xlsx	Primary data collected from the ICEBERG website newsletter sign-up form and consortium members' contact lists	20 MB	Not open access	Kaskas's Google Workspace
Media database	To communicate the progress and outcomes of the project to the media and through press releases	5.3	.xlsx	Primary data collected from consortium members' organisations; Secondary data from media websites and Meltwater Media Monitoring	20 MB	Not open access	Kaskas's Google Workspace
Visual media (posters)	To promote the project with targeted communication	5.4	.pdf, .jpg, .ai, .indd	Primary data generated from project information	20 GB	Open access	Kaskas's Google Workspace, ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams

2.5.3 To whom the data might be useful

The stakeholder data contains personal information and will not be reused by other researchers or third parties. Posters conveying ICEBERG project information may be useful for the following groups outside the project:

- Other projects and researchers conducting research in the Arctic region who want to connect and collaborate,
- Local communities who are interested in the activities of the ICEBERG project and want to participate,
- Educators in the field using posters for pedagogical purposes to showcase recent research developments.

2.5.4 Possibility of integration and re-use

The stakeholder data contains personal information and will not be reused by project partners following completion of the project. Stakeholder and media contact details will only be stored until the end of the project. ICEBERG visual media such as posters may be re-used by project partners in the future, for example to showcase their participation in a successful project or demonstrate their expertise.

2.6 WP6: Project Coordination and Management

2.6.1 Description

This work package is in charge of ensuring the efficient management of work, coordination and the timely production of high-quality outcomes, as well as submitting reports to the European Commission. In order to achieve this, WP6 coordinates work between partners and WPs and manages the data generated by the project (which includes producing the DMPs).

The data generated and used by WP6 is summarised in the next section.

2.4.2 Data summary for WP6

Table 6. Data summary for WP6

Type of data	Purpose	Task(s)	File format(s)	Origin	Expected size	Accessibility of data	Storage location
Official documents	Quality Assurance Plan (D6.1)	6.2	.txt, .pdf, .docx	Secondary data from EU GA and CA	3 MB	Open access	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams Official location of the EU GA?
Database created for DMP and EMP	First Data Management Plan (D6.2) Mid-term Data Management Plan (D6.4) Final Data Management Plan (D6.5) Ethics Management Plan (D6.3)	6.4	.xlsx, .txt, .pdf, .docx	Primary data collected from ICEBERG project consortium beneficiaries	3 MB	Open access (resulting management plans)	ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams

2.6.3 To whom the data might be useful

The data may be useful for the following groups outside the project:

- EC project officers and review boards who are checking that the management of quality, data, and ethics in the project are compliant with standards,
- Other projects and researchers conducting similar research who want to learn more about project coordination data,
- Stakeholders (e.g. community, decision makers, media) who want to understand the steps being taken to ensure the quality of the project and be reassured that the project will meet their expectations.

2.6.4 Possibility of integration and re-use

The data management plans are an iterative process, and data will be re-used, as well as added to throughout the project lifecycle. As the data contributes to the management of quality, data, and ethics in the project, key insights on best practice may be re-used and applied to other projects if applicable.

3 FAIR data

As part of making research data findable, accessible, interoperable, and reusable (FAIR), the DMP outlines below the management of data based on FAIR principles. For data from each WP in ICEBERG (as summarised in Section 2), this section will describe how the data is:

- **Findable:** others can find your data, for example in a repository, with metadata and a persistent identifier.
- **Accessible:** others can access your dataset as long as there are no issues, for example privacy issues.
- **Interoperable:** others and machines can open the files, for example with open file formats, and can combine this dataset with other datasets, for example through metadata standards.
- **Reusable:** others can understand the data and know how they can reuse it, for example if the data is documented and licensed.

3.1 Criteria for FAIR data

Table 7. Questions asked to determine how the data complies with each FAIR category (Horizon EU DMP Template, 2021)

Findable	Accessible	Interoperable	Reusable
<p>Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</p> <p>Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery?</p> <p>What metadata will be created if metadata standards do not exist in your discipline?</p> <p>What disciplinary or general standards will be followed?</p> <p>Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?</p> <p>Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?</p>	<p>Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository and be assigned an identifier (e.g. DOI)?</p> <p>Will all data be made openly available (including adopting open data formats)?</p> <p>Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?</p> <p>If access to (open) data is restricted, how is the access controlled?</p> <p>How long will the data remain available and findable?</p> <p>Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain license?</p> <p>Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?</p> <p>Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included?</p> <p>Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?</p>	<p>What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will be followed to make the data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines?</p> <p>Will community-endorsed interoperability best practices be followed?</p> <p>In case it is unavoidable that project specific ontologies or vocabularies are generated, will these be openly published to allow reusing, refining or extending them?</p> <p>Will the data include qualified references to other data (e.g. other data from the project, or datasets from previous research)?</p>	<p>How will documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use be provided (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?</p> <p>Will the data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible?</p> <p>Will the data be licensed using standard reuse licenses?</p> <p>Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?</p> <p>Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?</p> <p>Will data quality assurance processes be applied to the data?</p>

3.2 WP1 FAIR data

3.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All WP1 data is open access (Table 1) and will be made available in EU-compliant public repositories that provide the data with a persistent identifier to make the data findable. The public repositories are listed in the next section (Section 3.2.2). Standard persistent identifiers issued by these repositories are DOIs (Digital Object Identifiers) and URIs (Uniform Resource Identifiers). The public repositories provide a search field that supports simple keyword style searches as well as advanced searches (e.g. with Boolean operators). Search keywords supplied during data upload to repositories optimise the possibility for findability and potential re-use of the data.

Metadata standards for WP1 data are listed in Section 3.2.3. Rich metadata (additional information or details that are included with the data) include descriptions, file type, date created, and other relevant information that helps provide context and improve searchability, discovery, and visibility. WP1 data will be accompanied by metadata that is required by each specific repository. As a minimum standard, data in this WP will create metadata that has been provided in the DMP Data Summary table (description, purpose, file type, origin), in addition to authorship, date created, and search keywords. Metadata will be created in a way that allows easy harvesting and indexing by using established metadata standards (e.g. set by the public repository) and ensuring it is associated with a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI), to promote compatibility with indexing tools and systems

3.2.2 Making data accessible

All WP1 data (11 data types) are open access (Table 1). WP1 data will be made accessible through the following public repositories:

- PANGAEA - Data Publisher for Earth & Environmental Science
- Zenodo open repository
- OceanRep GEOMAR repository
- SIOS Data Management System (for Svalbard data)
- POLAR-PL - The Polish Polar Data Base
- Italian Arctic Data Centre (IADC) linked to SIOS
- Open repositories of specific journals (to be decided when generating publications)

PANGAEA, Zenodo and POLAR-PL assign DOIs to data as persistent identifiers, while IADC and OceanRep assign URIs. The SIOS Data Management System assigns a unique ID to each dataset.

WP1 data is accessible for free and made openly available under license CC BY 4.0 "Attribution 4.0 International". All data types in WP1 include an open data file format, allowing the data to be accessed by means of a free standard protocol. The data will remain available and findable via the public repositories after the project's end (and will be uploaded not later than two years after the completion of the ICEBERG project). Furthermore, model data will be included as open-source code in GitHub.

3.2.3 Making data interoperable

In order to make the data interoperable, WP1 applies the following metadata and methodological standards:

- ISO 19115: Metadata standard for describing geographic information and services
- IPTC: Photo Metadata standard
- ISO 17025: General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories
- ISO/IEC 10918: Guidelines for digital compression and coding of continuous-tone still images

To promote data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines, common and established methodologies for the field will be followed, and where possible adhere to the current scientific literature. For example, distributional data on stranded marine litter follows the protocol developed for the Sørkapp Marine Litter Cleanup project (Jóźwiak and Nawrot, 2021) and the Deep Dive Protocol (Falk-Andersson, 2021), further fine-tuned under ICEBERG.

3.2.4 Increase data re-use

WP1 permits re-use of data under license CC BY 4.0 "Attribution 4.0 International", in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement. The data is made freely available in the public domain via online repositories and will remain accessible to third parties after the end of the project. Documentation in the form of read-me files, xls/csv sheets, and supplementary material in publications containing information on methodology and other relevant information (e.g. variable definitions, units of measurements, etc.) will be provided to facilitate data re-use.

The following quality assurance and control methods are applied to WP1 data during or post collection/generation to promote re-use of high-quality data:

- Adhere to the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan) documentation guidelines (metadata standards for document names) to ensure file version control and provenance
- Outlier detection to identify and remove anomalies or errors in datasets
- Regular maintenance, calibration, and checking of equipment
- Checking for errors in sample handling and data entry (human error)
- Field team training and supervision
- Digital scale calibrated for usage in exact location
- Laboratory tests apply double sample analysis, calibration procedure and Certified Reference Materials (CRM) for control

Data quality is also assured through documentation of provenance to ensure reliability of the data. Provenance information including data origins/sources and who created the data is already available in this DMP (Section 2 Data Summary).

3.3 WP2 FAIR data

3.3.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Not all data from WP2 is open access (Table 2) due to sensitive and personal data (see Section 6.2 Data protection regulations). However, open access data will be made available in public repositories that provide the data with a persistent identifier to make the data findable. The public repositories are listed in the next section (Section 3.3.2). Standard persistent identifiers issued by these repositories are DOIs. The public repositories provide a search field that supports simple keyword style searches as well as advanced searches (e.g. with Boolean operators). Search keywords supplied during data upload to repositories optimise the possibility for findability and potential re-use of the data.

Metadata standards for WP2 data are listed in Section 3.3.3. Rich metadata (additional information or details that are included with the data) include descriptions, file type, date created, and other relevant information that helps provide context and improve searchability, discovery, and visibility. Open access WP2 data that is uploaded to repositories will be accompanied by metadata that is required by each specific repository. As a minimum standard, data in this WP will create metadata that has been provided in the DMP Data Summary table (description, purpose, file type, origin), in addition to authorship, date created, and search keywords. Metadata will be created in a way that allows easy harvesting and indexing by using established metadata standards (e.g.

set by the public repository) and ensuring it is associated with a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI), to promote compatibility with indexing tools and systems.

3.3.2 Making data accessible

Of the 29 data types generated by WP2, 15 data types are open access including the ones that require consent (Table 2). This is due to methods such as interviews and focus groups generating sensitive data that could identify participants (see Section 6.2 Data protection regulation). Of the open access data types, there are still some caveats and restrictions to making the data public. For example, survey data collecting pollution observations for the CBEM platform are displayed on the open access uMap interactive mapping tool. However, users may opt to provide contact information if they wish to be contacted by the researchers. This constitutes sensitive and personal data and will not be displayed on the CBEM platform. Many of the community activities data outputs (paper maps, empathy maps, photovoice entries) are expected to be open access but need to have consent from the community first.

WP2 open access data (note: not all data) will be made accessible through the following public repositories:

- SocArXiv open archive of the social sciences
- Zenodo open repository
- SSRN Social Science Research Network repository
- Data INRAE – The INRAE data repository
- Open platform for French public data (www.data.gouv.fr)
- Coastal Marine Litter Observatory (CMLO) online web platform
- Open repositories of specific journals (to be decided when generating publications)

SocArXiv, Zenodo, SSRN, Data INRAE, and the Open platform for French public data assign DOIs to data as persistent identifiers. Marine Litter Density Map Reports can be viewed through the CMLO platform, which assigns a unique ID to each data (can be accessed by clicking on the data points).

WP2 open access data types are accessible for free and made openly available under license CC BY 4.0 (with the exception of the CBEM survey data). However, it is noted that WaveLinks (used for the WP2 database of regulations) is a living database under constant development and the CC BY 4.0 license may change in future. Open access survey data for the CBEM is made accessible on the uMap platform, which uses the license Open Data Commons Open Database License (ODbL). The open access data types in WP2 include an open data file format (with the exception of map data), allowing the data to be accessed by means of a free standard protocol. However, digital cartographic data, such as the CBEM pollution observations and the litter density maps, are uploaded onto platforms that allow public accessibility. CBEM data is loaded onto uMap and litter density data and drone imagery are loaded on the CMLO online web platform, which makes viewing map data free and accessible. The data will remain available and findable via the public repositories after the project's end (and will be uploaded not later than two years after the completion of the ICEBERG project).

Although data types that are not open access (raw data such as interview transcripts) cannot be published due to data protection guidelines and regulation, these data may still generate open access outputs. For example, aggregated insights will be published in open access journal articles. Anonymised or aggregated data containing no personal data may be uploaded to public repositories. Only the project partners and individuals listed in the consent form are able to access the raw data. Restricted access of data is ensured by storage on password protected researcher/network drives, or on project shared drives (ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams) that are password and two-factor authentication protected.

3.3.3 Making data interoperable

- In order to make open access data interoperable, WP2 applies the following metadata and DCMI - Dublin Core Metadata Standard
- EXIF metadata standards for native images
- ZonMW metadata standards for health research
- OSPAR Commission metadata standards for map data
- uMap/OpenStreetMap metadata standards
- WaveLinks database metadata standards
- Bibliographical standards for legislative and policy document
- ISO 17025: General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories
- ISO 9001: Creating, implementing, and maintaining a Quality Management System
- ISO17043: General requirements for the competence of proficiency testing providers
- INFOGEST 2.0 standardized protocol for food digestion simulation in humans (Brodkorb et al. 2019)

To promote data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines, common and established methodologies for the field will be followed, and where possible adhere to the current scientific literature. For example, drone images will be collected using the SciDrones Marine Litter Data acquisition protocol (SciDrones PC Spinoff, n.d.). Contaminant samples analysed to study exposure will follow official laboratory methods from the French National Reference Laboratory (LABERCA). Field data collection (weathered plastic items, food items, etc.) follows standard social science protocols for interviews, focus groups, and surveys, including standard consent and information form templates. Personal information follows anonymisation protocols, for example using the tool QualiAnon (Nicolai et al., 2021).

3.3.4 Increase data re-use

WP2 permits re-use of open access data under licenses CC BY 4.0 and ODbL. The data is made freely available in the public domain via online repositories or open access platforms and will remain accessible to third parties after the end of the project. Documentation in the form of read-me files, xls/csv sheets, and supplementary material in publications containing information on methodology and other relevant information (e.g. appendices for consent form and information sheets) will be provided to facilitate data re-use. Data from WaveLinks and uMap are also downloadable as csv files, which allows users to extract and re-use the information in their own analyses.

The following quality assurance and control methods are applied to WP2 data during or post collection/generation to promote re-use of high-quality data:

- Adhere to the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan) documentation guidelines (metadata standards for document names) to ensure file version control and provenance
- Lab methods that are ISO 17025 accredited, so QA/QC are included to monitor analytical performances
- Lab sample processing uses experimental replicates
- Statistical analyses of lab results using the software GraphPad Prism 9.1 to detect anomalies or outliers
- Climate data (CMIP6 decadal predictions and climate indicators) are post-processed using software to run diagnostic skills assessments
- Cross-checking transcripts for key interviews
- Intercoder evaluation for transcripts
- Checking for errors in data entry and handling (e.g. assuring that transferring data from one storage location to another one will not affect the data)
- Community participant training on SciDrones Marine Litter Data acquisition protocol for optimizing drone flight preparation
- Automated pre-processing of collected drone images to ensure data integrity and reducing faults or corrupted data

- Training/capacity building workshops for uMap to familiarise users with capabilities and functions
- Guideline/manuals for citizens and curators to use uMap
- Quality check by local curators for CBEM platform data
- Data entry protocols in CBEM survey that reduce entry error
- Training of citizens for maintenance of time-lapse cameras and how to conduct regular quality checks
- Regular quality checks by citizens for functionality of equipment, quality of data, and assessment of data captured (e.g. is the data suitable for future methods?)
- Quality check by WaveLinks database managers

Data quality is also assured through documentation of provenance to ensure reliability of the data. Provenance information including data origins/sources and who created the data is already available in this DMP (Section 2 Data Summary).

3.4 WP3 FAIR data

3.4.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Part of the data generated in WP3 is not open access (Table 3) since much data generated in WP3 is interview data, which includes potentially sensitive insights and personal information (see Section 6.2 Data protection regulations). However, these data will generate open access outputs (e.g. aggregated insights, anonymised data, database), which will be published in open access journal articles or uploaded to public repositories that assign persistent identifiers such as DOIs. Data on local, national, regional and international marine pollutants governance is the only data type in this WP to be open access. This data will be made available on Zenodo, which assign DOIs. A database of regulations and policies will constitute another open-access dataset. These repositories provide a search field that supports simple keyword style searches as well as advanced searches (e.g. with Boolean operators). Search keywords supplied during data upload to repositories optimise the possibility for findability and potential re-use of the data.

Metadata standards for WP3 data are listed in Section 3.4.3. The WP2 marine pollutants governance data that is uploaded to repositories will be accompanied by metadata that is required by each specific repository. As a minimum standard, data in this WP will create metadata that has been provided in the DMP Data Summary table (description, purpose, file type, origin), in addition to authorship, date created, and search keywords. Metadata will be created in a way that allows easy harvesting and indexing by using established metadata standards (e.g. set by the public repository) and ensuring it is associated with a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI), to promote compatibility with indexing tools and systems.

3.4.2 Making data accessible

Of the 8 data types generated by WP3, only 1 data type will eventually be open access (Table 3). This is due to the main data type (interviews) generating sensitive data that could identify participants (see Section 6.2 Data protection regulations). Although raw data such as interview transcripts cannot be published due to data protection guidelines and regulation, these data may still generate open access outputs. For example, aggregated insights will be published in open access journal articles. Anonymised or aggregated data containing no personal data may be uploaded to public repositories.

Interviews with political stakeholders may be open access if interviewees consent and the transcripts are partly anonymised. Only the project partners and individuals listed in the consent form are able to access the raw data. Restricted access of data is ensured by storage on password protected researcher/network drives, or on project shared drives (ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams) that are password and two-factor authentication protected.

WP2 open access data (marine pollutants governance data and aggregated insights from interviews) will be made accessible through the following public repositories:

- SocArXiv open archive of the social sciences
- Zenodo open repository
- SSRN Social Science Research Network repository
- Aggregated insights from interviews will be submitted in publications to open access journals (to be decided when generating publications)

SocArXiv, Zenodo, SSRN, and open access journals assign DOIs to data as persistent identifiers. WP3 open access data types are accessible for free and made openly available under license CC BY 4.0 "Attribution 4.0 International". The data will remain available and findable via the public repositories after the project's end (and will be uploaded not later than two years after the completion of the ICEBERG project).

3.4.3 Making data interoperable

In order to make open access marine pollutants governance data interoperable, WP3 will apply bibliographic standards for legislative and policy documents. To promote data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines, common and established methodologies for the field will be followed. Field data collection follows standard social science protocols for interviews and focus groups, including standard consent and information form templates. Personal information follows anonymisation protocols, for example using the tool QualiAnon (Nicolai et al., 2021).

3.4.4 Increase data re-use

WP3 permits re-use of open access data (marine pollutants governance data and aggregated insights from interviews) under license CC BY 4.0. The data is made freely available in the public domain via online repositories and will remain accessible to third parties after the end of the project. Supplementary material in publications containing information on methodology and other relevant information (e.g. appendices for consent form and information sheets) will be provided to facilitate data re-use.

The following quality assurance and control methods are applied to WP3 data during or post collection/generation to promote re-use of high-quality data:

- Adhere to the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan) documentation guidelines (metadata standards for document names) to ensure file version control and provenance
- Cross-checking transcripts for key interviews
- Intercoder evaluation for transcripts
- Checking for errors in data entry and handling (e.g. assuring that transferring data from one storage location to another one will not affect the data)

Data quality is also assured through documentation of provenance to ensure reliability of the data. Provenance information including data origins/sources and who created the data is already available in this DMP (Section 2 Data Summary).

3.5 WP4 FAIR data

3.5.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Most of the data generated by WP4 is not open access (Table 4) due to sensitive and personal data (see Section 6.2 Data protection regulations). Technically, no raw data generated by WP4 is open access, however, some

consortium co-creation data will be screenshotted from their original media (PowerPoint, MiroBoard, Mentimeter) and presented in public level reports and publication. Thus, this section will refer to the provisions made for FAIR management of the reports that feature WP4 open access data. Public level reports and publications will be made available in repositories that provide the data with a DOI persistent identifier to make the data findable. The public repositories provide a search field that supports simple keyword style searches as well as advanced searches (e.g. with Boolean operators). Search keywords supplied during data upload to repositories optimise the possibility for findability and potential re-use of the data.

Metadata standards for WP4 data are listed in Section 3.5.3. Rich metadata (additional information or details that are included with the data) include descriptions, file type, date created, and other relevant information that helps provide context and improve searchability, discovery, and visibility. Open access WP4 data that is uploaded to repositories will be accompanied by metadata that is required by each specific repository. As a minimum standard, data in this WP will create metadata that has been provided in the DMP Data Summary table (description, purpose, file type, origin), in addition to authorship, date created, and search keywords. Metadata will be created in a way that allows easy harvesting and indexing by using established metadata standards (e.g. set by the public repository) and ensuring it is associated with a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI), to promote compatibility with indexing tools and systems.

3.5.2 Making data accessible

Of the 17 data types generated by WP4, 4 data types are open access including one which requires consent (Table 4). These data are derived from consortium co-creation workshops and shared via public level reports. The other data types are not open access due to methods such as interviews and focus groups generating sensitive data that could identify participants (see Section 6.2 Data protection regulations). However, these data may still generate open access outputs (e.g. aggregated insights, anonymised data), which will be published in open access journal articles or uploaded to public repositories that assign persistent identifiers such as DOIs. Only the project partners and individuals listed in the consent form are able to access the raw data. Restricted access of data is ensured by storage on password protected researcher/network drives, or on project shared drives (ICEBERG MS Teams) that are password and two-factor authentication protected.

WP4 open access data (consortium co-creation data and aggregated interview/focus group insights) will be made accessible through the following public repositories:

- SocArXiv open archive of the social sciences
- Zenodo open repository
- SSRN Social Science Research Network repository
- Aggregated insights from interviews will be submitted in publications to open access journals (to be decided when generating publications)

SocArXiv, Zenodo, SSRN, and open access journals assign DOIs to data as persistent identifiers. WP4 open access data types are accessible for free and made openly available under license CC BY 4.0 "Attribution 4.0 International". The data will remain available and findable via the public repositories after the project's end (and will be uploaded not later than two years after the completion of the ICEBERG project).

3.5.3 Making data interoperable

To promote interoperability within and across disciplines, common and established methodologies for the field will be followed. Field data collection follows standard social science protocols for interviews and focus groups, including standard consent and information form templates. Personal information follows anonymisation protocols, for example using the tool QualiAnon (Nicolai et al., 2021).

3.5.4 Increase data re-use

WP4 permits re-use of open access data (consortium co-creation data and aggregated interview/focus group insights) under license CC BY 4.0. The data is made freely available in the public domain via online repositories and will remain accessible to third parties after the end of the project. Supplementary material in publications containing information on methodology and other relevant information (e.g. appendices for consent form and information sheets) will be provided to facilitate data re-use.

The following quality assurance and control methods are applied to WP4 data during or post collection/generation to promote re-use of high-quality data:

- Adhere to the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan) documentation guidelines (metadata standards for document names) to ensure file version control and provenance
- Cross-checking transcripts for key interviews
- Intercoder evaluation for transcripts
- Checking for errors in data entry and handling (e.g. assuring that transferring data from one storage location to another one will not affect the data)

Data quality is also assured through documentation of provenance to ensure reliability of the data. Provenance information including data origins/sources and who created the data is already available in this DMP (Section 2 Data Summary).

3.6 WP5 FAIR data

3.6.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Most data from WP5 is not open access (Table 5) since the majority of data generated in this WP represent stakeholder contact details, which includes personal information (see Section 6.2 Data protection regulations). Visual media with research data (e.g. scientific posters) is the only data type in this WP to be made open access. This data is not typically uploaded to repositories; however, it may be made available on the ICEBERG website or conference websites and proceedings. For example, if a poster was submitted to the EGU (European Geosciences Union) Assembly, metadata including the abstract (describes purpose, methods, key findings), authors, and date of presentation would be associated with the poster. This abstract would be uploaded to the Copernicus Publications repository and assigned a DOI. This repository provides a search field, which would promote the possibility for findability and potential re-use of the data.

As a minimum standard, data in this WP will create metadata that has been provided in the DMP Data Summary table (description, purpose, file type, origin) in addition to authorship, date created, and search keywords if uploaded to a repository/conference website.

3.6.2 Making data accessible

Of the 4 data types generated by WP5, only 1 data type is open access (Table 5). These data are derived from available project information and shared via visual media (e.g. posters). The other data types are not open access due to the inclusion of personal data (see Section 6.2 Data protection regulations). Restricted access of data is ensured by storage on password protected researcher and company drives, or on project shared drives (ICEBERG OneDrive, MS Teams) that are password and two-factor authentication protected.

WP5 visual media are made publicly accessible through the ICEBERG website, social media pages, and press releases. Depending on the purpose and target audience, the visual media may be included on conference websites and proceedings, which may be associated with a DOI. The posters are accessible for free and made

openly available under license CC BY 4.0. The data will remain available and findable after the project's end as long as the website will remain functional.

3.6.3 Making data interoperable

The visual media data is made interoperable through standardised file formats for the graphic design discipline. In order for project partners and third parties to view and use posters, these are converted to an easy to access machine-readable format such as pdf or jpg. Visual media are subjected to a check for cross-platform support, ensuring that content can be displayed and accessed on a wide range of devices, including computers, smartphones, and print media.

3.6.4 Increase data re-use

WP5 permits re-use of open access data (promotional visual media e.g. posters) under license CC BY 4.0. The following quality assurance and control methods are applied to WP5 data during or post collection/generation to promote re-use of high-quality data:

- Adhere to the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan) documentation guidelines (metadata standards for document names) to ensure file version control and provenance
- Using file version control to track changes and updates made to visual media content
- Quality check for cross-platform support to ensure that visual media content can be displayed and accessed on a wide range of devices (e.g. smartphone vs. computer) and for print media
- Establishing project guidelines (e.g. ICEBERG Communication Guidelines) to monitor and regulate the use of visual media content
- Establishing feedback mechanisms to gather feedback from partners on the usability and effectiveness of visual media, and use this input to continually improve and enhance them

Data quality is also assured through documentation of provenance to ensure reliability of the data. Provenance information including data origins/sources and who created the data is already available in this DMP (Section 2 Data Summary).

3.7 WP6 FAIR data

3.7.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

All data generated by WP6 is open access (Table 6). Deliverables are all public level reports that will be made available in repositories that provide a DOI persistent identifier to make the data findable. The public repositories provide a search field that supports simple keyword style searches as well as advanced searches (e.g. with Boolean operators). Search keywords supplied during data upload to repositories optimise the possibility for findability and potential re-use of the data.

Deliverables that are uploaded to repositories will be accompanied by metadata that is required by each specific repository. As a minimum standard, data in this WP will create metadata that has been provided in the DMP Data Summary table (description, purpose, file type, origin), in addition to authorship, date created, and search keywords. Metadata will be created in a way that allows easy harvesting and indexing by using established metadata standards (e.g. set by the public repository) and ensuring it is associated with a persistent identifier (e.g. DOI), to promote compatibility with indexing tools and systems.

3.7.2 Making data accessible

The data from WP6 will be shared via public level reports and uploaded to Zenodo. Since Zenodo is an open research data repository that is hosted and managed by CERN and funded by the European Commission, it would be appropriate to upload project deliverables to this repository. This multidisciplinary repository accepts multiple data types, publications, and software and assigns a Digital Object Identifier (DOI).

WP6 data are accessible for free and made openly available under license CC BY 4.0 "Attribution 4.0 International". The data will remain available and findable via the public repositories after the project's end. In addition, once approved by the European Commission, the deliverables will be available on our website. Data from WP6 will be uploaded in a timely manner as the deliverables follow a predetermined schedule with fixed deadlines.

3.7.3 Making data interoperable

The project has created a QAP (D6.1) that states naming conventions for files. A template for deliverables created by WP5 also includes a descriptive metadata page.

3.7.4 Increase data re-use

WP6 permits re-use of open access data (public deliverables) under license CC BY 4.0. The following quality assurance and control methods are applied to WP6 data during or post collection/generation to promote re-use of high-quality data:

- Adhere to the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1 Quality Assurance Plan) documentation guidelines (metadata standards for document names) to ensure file version control and provenance
- Using file version control to track changes and updates made to deliverables
- Establishing feedback mechanisms to gather feedback from partners on all deliverables as a quality check

Data quality is also assured through documentation of provenance to ensure reliability of the data. Provenance information including data origins/sources and who created the data is already available in this DMP (Section 2 Data Summary).

4 Other research outputs

4.1 Research outputs besides data

Other research outputs for the ICEBERG project are:

- Models
- Policy briefs
- User guides
- White papers
- Databases
- Toolboxes
- Online citizen participation platform
- Website, blogs, and social media pages

4.2 FAIR management of research outputs

The considerations pertaining to FAIR data are applied to non-data outputs, for example use of metadata standards and uploading of outputs to open repositories. The following are examples of how the ICEBERG project plans to manage and share research outputs based on FAIR data principles:

- As per the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1), the partners must – as soon as possible (but not before a decision on their possible protection) – disseminate results, for example, through online channels (website/social media platforms), peer-reviewed publications (open access), or conference presentations
- As per the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1), the partners must follow standards for bibliographic metadata of open access research outputs (see Section 4.3)
- Deliverables (policy briefs, user guides, white papers, databased, toolboxes) are public level dissemination and will be uploaded to ICEBERG website, open repositories and assigned a DOI
- Outputs uploaded to open repositories will follow the repository's metadata standards, providing as much detail as possible using standardised vocabularies used in the corresponding discipline
- Quality assurance in calibre of deliverables through version history tracking and reviews by the project management team and consortium partners (and also in some cases, the project ethics advisor and advisory board)
- Deliverables provide provenance metadata (version history and authors) and descriptive metadata (e.g. work package number, dissemination level), using the template created by UOULU and KASKAS
- Online citizen participation platform is hosted by open access interactive mapping tool uMap, which is free and open source
- Model code for the assessment of impacts of pollutants in seawater will be made available on GitHub following the repository's metadata standards
- Use dissemination channels such as the website, blog posts, and social media pages to increase discovery of outputs and promote re-use by interested third parties
- Dissemination measures should be consistent with the 'DECO strategy' (D5.2), following guidelines to increase impact and re-use by interested third parties
- All partners will contribute to dissemination activities to promoting collaboration and knowledge-sharing within the project research disciplines and across disciplines (thereby promoting re-use of information)

4.3 Open access to research outputs

As per the ICEBERG QAP (D6.1), each partner must ensure open access (free of charge online access for any user) to all peer-reviewed scientific publications relating to its results.

Partners must:

- As soon as possible and at the latest on publication, deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or final peer-reviewed manuscript accepted for publication in a repository for scientific publications
- Aim to deposit at the same time as above, the research data needed to validate the results presented in the deposited scientific publications
- Ensure open access to the deposited publication via the repository at the latest on publication, if an electronic version is available for free via the publisher, or within six months of publication (twelve months for publications in the social sciences and humanities)
- Ensure open access to the deposited publication via the repository to the bibliographic metadata that identifies the deposited publication

The bibliographic metadata must be in a standard format and must include all of the following:

- The terms "European Union (EU)" and "Horizon Europe"
- The name of the action, acronym and grant number
- The publication date and length of embargo period if applicable
- A persistent identifier

5 Allocation of resources

5.1 Costs for FAIR data and research

The costs for making data and research outputs FAIR are costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, and security. Indirect costs (e.g. entire RDM teams at institutes) would be associated with higher expenses, but they would not need to be covered by the project budget. The resources associated with these costs are listed below.

Potential direct costs for making the data FAIR in the ICEBERG project are:

- Time used by partners for data curation, documentation, and providing rich metadata
- Time used by partners for uploading of metadata and datasets to open repositories
- Opportunity costs of time spent by partners on data management instead of other project tasks
- Open access costs paid to journals for publication of articles that are publicly accessible
- Costs for resources required for data storage and backup (e.g. Miro Board costs)
- Costs for maintaining data infrastructure and systems for long-term data accessibility (e.g. yearly website fees)
- Costs for hiring external expertise in data management (e.g. ICEBERG Ethics Advisor for consulting on ethics of data sharing and security)

Potential indirect costs for making the data FAIR in the ICEBERG project are:

- Costs for resources required for institution data storage and backup (e.g. institute network drives)
- Costs for personnel at partner institutions to advise in research data management (e.g. data protection officers, RDM units)

Partner effort (measured in person-months or PMs) is covered by project funding and would include time used by partners to enact FAIR data protocols. As per the EU GA, the activities related to the DMP (such as providing guidance on data management and open access issues and preparing the DMP) will cost about 0.5 PM for the whole duration of the project. Open access publication costs and compensation mechanisms for external expertise are also included in the project budget.

The project-wide storage locations for data include various cloud storage servers (e.g. OneDrive, Dropbox) and online tools (e.g. MS TEAMS). The associated costs for storage in network drives are incurred by the partner institutes, with the main project storage costs (ICEBERG OneDrive/MS Teams) covered by the UOULU IT infrastructure. The cost for the ICEBERG Miro Board has been incurred by project partner WoA. Long term accessibility of the website will be maintained and funded by KASKAS. Costs for hiring RDM personnel are incurred by the partner institutes.

5.2 Data management responsibilities

All individuals in the project have some responsibility for data management. The below table outlines the key roles and responsibilities for data management (Table 8).

Table 8. Roles and responsibilities for data management in the ICEBERG project

Role	Responsibilities
Data provider/researcher	<p>Describe the data using appropriate Metadata or discipline standards</p> <p>Apply quality assurance protocols when generating or processing data (and post-processing)</p> <p>Deposit open access data in open repositories or publish scientific publications in open access journals</p> <p>Participate in dissemination activities (e.g. conferences, writing blog posts for the ICEBERG website) to promote sharing of data, with the support of the project DECO team</p>
WP leads (in collaboration with Task leads)	<p>Provide input to the data management plan and check accuracy of expected data types</p> <p>Implement data management protocols from the ICEBERG DMP in their respective WPs (including FAIR principles)</p> <p>Contacting the project management team and ethics advisor in case of ethical and privacy issues with data</p> <p>Participate in dissemination activities (e.g. conferences, writing blog posts for the ICEBERG website) to promote sharing of data, with the support of the project DECO team</p>
Project coordination team (WP6)	<p>Monitor data management activities and deadlines and send reminders to partners</p> <p>Offer support and further guidance for filling out the data surveys</p> <p>Monitor that open results are deposited in public repositories</p> <p>Participate in dissemination activities (e.g. conferences, writing blog posts for the ICEBERG website) to promote sharing of data, with the support of the project DECO team</p>
Data management team (T6.4 leads)	<p>Develop the data management plans throughout the project lifecycle in cooperation with the project partners</p> <p>Request and compile information about data generated or used by partners</p> <p>Ask partners for missing information or clarifications</p> <p>Provide support and provide solutions for specific issues about project data management</p>

Role	Responsibilities
DECO team	Promote communication and sharing of data to broad and general audiences Support partners in communicating and sharing data Provide platforms (e.g. social media, blog) for partners to share data Organise events to disseminate data and outputs
Ethics advisor	Advise on the ethical dimensions of data management, for example data protection and security Support the writing of the data management plans Support the project management and data management teams in providing guidance to WP leads and partners around data protection Work with partners and project management team to resolve critical issues around data ethics

Furthermore, the DESCA ICEBERG Consortium Agreement Attachment 6 also defines the following roles concerning processing of personal data:

- Data controller: the natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which, alone or jointly with others, determines the purposes and means of the Processing of Personal Data, where the purposes and means of such Processing are determined by the European Union or Member State law, as per Article 4(7) GDPR
- Data processor: a natural or legal person, public authority, agency or other body which processes Personal Data on behalf of a Data Controller, as per Article 4(8) GDPR

As per these definitions, the project will have many data controllers and processors. Typically, the data controllers will be the partner institutes, and are listed with their legal names, for example Helmholtz-Zentrum für Umweltforschung GmbH (trade name: UFZ). Who the data processors are will depend on the methods used to collect or generate data. For example, if using a survey method, the data processor would be the third-party survey platform (e.g. LimeSurvey GmbH). For interview methodology, the data processors may be the partner institutes themselves (unless a third-party service is used, for example a professional transcription service).

Of the 16 consortium partner institutions, all have data protection officers except six who do not have a dedicated role for data protection. However, these institutions have a responsible person for data management who may deal in the aspects of data protection.

6 Data security

6.1 Provisions for data security

Data (with the exception of personal data) is stored at a minimum for 5 years according to the EU GA (record-keeping for 5 years after final payment; pg. 13, Point 6), but preferably for 10 years according to good scientific practice (DFG, 2019). Personal data is deleted after anonymisation or after project completion at the latest. Open access data will be deposited and stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation.

The following provisions are in place for data security, which includes data recovery as well as secure storage and transfer of sensitive data:

- Implementing data backup and recovery procedures to prevent data loss (e.g. backing up files in the ICEBERG OneDrive, making shared folders for WPs)
- Implementing access controls and authentication mechanisms to ensure that only authorized individuals can access sensitive data (e.g. anonymization, blurring people's face, multifactor authentication to access the ICEBERG OneDrive)
- Where possible, implementing secure file transfer protocols such as SFTP (Secure File Transfer Protocol) or HTTPS (Hypertext Transfer Protocol Secure) when transferring sensitive data between researchers (e.g. using ICEBERG OneDrive to share data, which uses HTTPS to encrypt data transferred between researcher drives to OneDrive servers)
- Implementing data anonymisation for interviews and focus group data to reduce the risk of personal data exposure
- Explicitly specifying in consent forms who has access and rights to raw data

In addition, project partners with their own institutional policies for handling and secure storage of sensitive data will be required to adhere to these protocols. The policies and protocols can be found here:

- University of Oulu Research Data Management Guide (<https://libguides.oulu.fi/researchdata>)
- University of Lapland Principles (<https://www.ulapland.fi/EN/About-us/Our-principles/Data-protection>)
- University of Kiel Data Management Plan (<https://www.datamanagement.uni-kiel.de/de/ressourcen/dokumente/cau-dmp-recommendations-pdf>)
- UFZ Guidelines on Research Data Management (<https://rdm.pages.ufz.de/guidelines/>)
- GEOMAR Research Data Policy (https://doi.org/10.3289/data_policy_V1_2022)
- SAI uses: Personal Data Protection Policy of the University of Akureyri (<https://www.unak.is/english/university/strategies-and-policies/personal-data-protection-policy-of-the-university-of-akureyri>)
- INRAE Personal Data Protection Policy (https://www.inrae.fr/sites/default/files/pdf/PolitiqueProtectionDonnees_INRAE-Uk_0.pdf)
- AIRCentre Personal Data Protection Guide (https://www.aircentre.org/wp-content/uploads/2023/11/Personal_Data_Protection_Guide.pdf)
- Barcelona Supercomputing Center Policy (<https://www.bsc.es/res-intranet/legal-notice>)
- Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche (https://www.rpd.cnr.it/wp/?page_id=612)

6.2 Data protection regulations

This section will present the regulations for data protection that are relevant to the case studies. See Section 7.3.2 Personal data for instances and groups that these regulations apply to.

6.2.1 GDPR

Greenland, Iceland, and Svalbard are all subject to the GDPR, or Regulation (EU) 2016/679 (General Data Protection Regulation). Listed below is a summary of three GDPR articles relating to processing of personal data that are particularly relevant for the ICEBERG project.

Article 5 of the GDPR states that processing of personal data must comply with *all* six principles:

- Lawfulness, fairness and transparency: data is processed fairly, lawfully and in a transparent manner in relation to the data subject
- Purpose limitation: data is collected for specified, explicit and legitimate purposes and not processed in a manner incompatible with those purposes
- Data minimization: data is adequate, relevant and limited to what is necessary to the purpose for which they are processed
- Accuracy: data is accurate and up to date, with steps taken to ensure inaccurate personal data are erased or rectified without delay
- Storage limitation: data which permits identification of data subjects are kept for no longer than what is necessary to the purpose for which they are processed
- Integrity and confidentiality: data is processed in a secure manner

Article 6 of the GDPR states that processing of personal data must satisfy *at least one* of the following conditions:

- Data processing is carried out with the data subject's consent
- Data processing is necessary for the performance of a contract with the data subject;
- Data processing is necessary for compliance with a legal obligation
- Data processing is necessary in order to protect the vital interests of the data subject
- Data processing is necessary for the public interest or in the exercise of official authority
- Data processing is necessary for the legitimate interests of the data controller, except where overridden by the interests of the data subject

The ICEBERG project will always comply with the first condition – that is informed consent must be obtained from the data subject (see Section 7.2). As per Article 7 of the GDPR, the conditions for consent for data processing are:

- The data controller must be able to demonstrate that the data subject has consented to processing of their personal data
- The request for consent must be presented in a manner which is clearly distinguishable from the other matters in the consent form, in an intelligible and easily accessible form, using clear and plain language
- The data subject has the right to withdraw their consent at any time (in an easy way) and are informed of this prior to giving consent
- When determining if consent is freely given, consider if the performance of a contract is conditional on consent to the processing of personal data that is not necessary for the performance of that contract (in other words, consent should not be coerced or required for something unrelated to the purpose of the research)

6.2.2 Country specific regulations

In addition, there are several country specific legislations that cover processing personal data, formalities to obtain consent to process personal data, and special rules when processing personal data about children and vulnerable groups. The relevant regulations of the case study countries are:

- Greenland: Danish Personal Data Act in effect from the 25th of May 2018
- Iceland: Act on the Protection of Privacy in regards to the Processing of Personal Data, No. 77/2000
- Svalbard: Norwegian Law on the Processing of Personal Data (Personal Data Act) in effect from the 15th of June 2018

The relevant regulations of the consortium partner countries are (note: only those collecting personal data are listed):

- Finnish Data Protection Act (1050/2018)
- German Federal Data Protection Act of 30 June 2017
- Spanish Organic Law 3/2018 of December 5 on Protection of Personal Data and Guarantee of Digital Rights

6.3 Third parties

Some data in the ICEBERG project is processed by third parties. In the event that the third party is used to process data, a data processing agreement according to Article 28 GDPR (Processor) is in place. The below table presents the third parties used, their purpose, and their data protection agreement.

Table 9. Third parties who handle data from the ICEBERG project

Third party	Purpose	Data protection agreement
Miro Board	Digital whiteboard platform used to generate and display data co-created by the consortium	https://miro.com/legal/vendor-data-processing-addendum/
Webropol	Survey tool used to collect data from consortium members	https://webropol.co.uk/privacy-policy/
Mentimeter	Survey tool used to collect data from consortium members	https://www.mentimeter.com/dpa-statement
LimeSurvey	Survey tool used to collect data on pollution observations from citizens for the CBEM platform	https://www.limesurvey.org/privacy-notice

Third party	Purpose	Data protection agreement
uMap	Used as the CBEM platform to display pollution observations data	https://umap.org/wp-content/uploads/2022/03/2022.03.23-Private-Information-Protection-Policy.pdf
Mailchimp	Used to collect and store stakeholder email lists for ICEBERG newsletter	https://mailchimp.com/en/about/security/
Microsoft OneDrive and Teams	Data storage	https://www.microsoft.com/licensing/docs/view/Microsoft-Products-and-Services-Data-Protection-Addendum-DPA
Dropbox	Data storage	https://www.dropbox.com/privacy
Google Cloud Storage	Data storage	https://cloud.google.com/terms/data-processing-addendum

7 Ethics

ICEBERG established an Ethics Management Plan (D6.3) in M9 to define ethical principles, develop an ethics evaluation framework, and ensure compliance with EU/national legal and ethical requirements in the countries where the project's activities are carried out. This section provides an update of the Ethics Management Plan (D6.3) which was a revised version of Section 7 (Ethics) and Section 8 (Other issues) of the First Data Management Plan (D6.2).

7.1 Ethical governance procedures

Of the 16 consortium partners, six institutions have an ethics committee. In addition, two institutions are in the process of setting up an ethics committee and one institution has an internal research board. Some institutions also have legal departments and data protection officers that ensure compliance with personal data protection.

The following ethical governance procedures will be followed:

- CAU Kiel Guidelines for good scientific practice
- DFG Guide to Good Scientific Practice
- European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity
- Ethics for researchers- Facilitating Research Excellence in FP7
- Finnish National Board on Research Integrity (TENK guidelines 2019)
- French Office for Research Integrity (Ofis) guidelines
- High Council for Evaluation of Research and Higher Education (Hcéres) guidelines
- Rules for Safeguarding Good Scientific Practice at the UFZ
- Svalbard Environmental Protection Act
- University of Aegean ethical regulations (followed by SCI as a spinoff company)
- University of Akureyri Code of Ethics
- Ilisimatusarfik's guidelines for ethical research (2024)

In addition, the ICEBERG project met with Arctic Hub in Greenland (<https://arctichub.gl/>) and is featured on the Arctic Hub Connect Map that displays research projects in Greenland.

7.2 Ethical considerations

The following are ethics and legal issues that could have an impact on data sharing in the ICEBERG project:

- The project involves research with Indigenous and non-Indigenous individuals and communities. It engages with adults, youth, and elders. The project must consider how to share data with local communities and Indigenous communities, and how to ensure that the data benefits them. See Section 7.4 Human participation
- Recruitment of participants among field site communities must take into consideration inclusiveness and aim for diverse representation regarding gender, identity, social-cultural and socio-economic factors. However, participant selection is limited to those that can give informed consent
- In case of the possibility for unexpected findings in the results or in the engagement with the informants, they will be handled according to the established procedures at each organisation, referring participants beforehand to the relevant support services. In the case of Greenland, ethical procedures will be

elaborated and will take into account the ongoing process in Greenland to establish ethical guidelines for research with Greenlandic communities

As per the ICEBERG Description of the Action (DoA) Section 4 Ethics Self-Assessment, possible ethical issues will be minimised by:

- Developing ethical principles that will be implemented in the research process such as the principle to let participants have their name shown in the data as a knowledge holder if they wish, and so, aiming to better respect Indigenous perspectives and rights while at the same time taking precautions to avoid potential tensions
- Only collecting data that is necessary for the research context

Ensuring that no personal data is transferred between partners in different countries.

7.3 Informed consent and personal data

7.3.1 Informed consent

All study participants will be asked for their written informed consent in paper or electronic format for taking part in the study (participation or audio/visual recording) and for data processing before the start of an interview, focus group, or a survey. Informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation will be included in the participant information sheet that accompanies the consent form dealing with personal data.

Voluntariness and informed consent will be ensured by:

- Plain language written consent forms and participant information sheets will be provided, as well as oral explanations of the purpose and format of obtaining data
- Clear explanation will be provided on all parts of the consent form prior to any interview or stakeholder engagement, with opportunities for participants to ask questions
- The researcher will provide honest and thorough answers for any questions asked about the consent form or research
- During the consent process, each researcher will ensure that the information is fully comprehended by the individuals being interviewed, thereby allowing for an informed decision to be made
- Ensure that the individual understands that they can withdraw from the study at any time and voice any criticism, disappointment or negative feedback to the interviewer without penalty or repercussions
- The consent form will also include an option for the participant to request a copy of the document prior to publication, and to receive acknowledgment/recognition
- Participants who wish to be named when quoted will be provided a chance to review the quote(s) they have provided prior to publication to double check that their knowledge is well represented and correctly understood by the researchers
- The researcher will document the consent process by keeping detailed records of all discussions, questions asked, and the individual's consent (in field notebooks)
- The consent form outlines how data will be processed, stored, used, shared and potentially re-used. It will also include the contact details of the project coordinators to facilitate participants' questions, requests, and possible withdrawal

Each participant will be provided with a comprehensive Information Form (see Appendix 2) detailing the purpose, scope, and methodology of the research, along with any potential risks and benefits involved. Participants will

also receive a Written Consent Form (see Appendix 3) which they will review and sign along with the signature of the researcher(s) before engaging in any study-related activities. This form will outline their rights, including the option to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence, ensuring that informed and voluntary participation is maintained throughout the research process. The two documents are written in clear, accessible language to foster transparency and understanding. The two documents can be provided in English, Danish, Icelandic, Norwegian and Greenlandic. A new version of both the Information Sheet and the Written Consent Form (from versions previously presented in D6.3 Ethics Management Plan) as well as a new Written Consent Form for Youth in English and Danish (see Appendix 4) were used in the 2025 field season and are now available in the Appendices in this document.

7.3.2 Personal data

As per the ICEBERG DoA Section 4 Ethics Self-Assessment, personal data will be treated according to personal data processing legislation – The General Data Protection Regulation 2016/679 and local personal data protection regulations in EU and non-EU/EEA partner countries. See Section 6.2 of this document for relevant data protection regulations followed by the ICEBERG project. No personal data is to be transferred between partners in different countries unless consent given by the informant(s). Only anonymised or aggregated data will be shared with partners. Personal research data will be destroyed after the end of the research project.

The DESCA ICEBERG Consortium Agreement Attachment 6 defines the roles of data controller and data processor. As per these definitions, the data controllers will typically be the partner institutes, while the data processors will depend on the methods used to collect or generate data. ICEBERG partner institutes are the data controllers bound by data control laws and regulations while those bound by data processing laws and regulations can be both ICEBERG partners and third parties if/when third parties somehow use or process the ICEBERG data. For example, if using a survey method, the data processor would be the third-party survey platform (e.g. LimeSurvey GmbH). For interview methodology, the data processors may be the partner institutes themselves (unless a third-party service is used, for example a professional transcription service). In the case that a third party is used to process data, a data processing agreement according to Article 28 GDPR (Processor) is in place.

Personal data processed in the ICEBERG project are:

- Data collected in the Informed Consent form (names and postal address or electronic address in case participants wish to receive the results of the research)
- Signed consent forms
- Gender, age (the participants will include people aged over 18 years of age, at the exception of 16-year-old students who are part of a class where the teacher operates a drone for marine litter mapping)
- Main occupation (e.g. for interviews with stakeholders and political actors)
- Area of living (region/city/area code)
- Photographs and video materials (e.g. from art-based methods)

Sensitive personal data concerning mostly indirect health related (not medical data), racial, or ethnicity data gathered from the interviews and focus groups will be processed in the study. Sensitive data is processed on the legal basis of scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, as outlined in Article 9(2) of the GDPR. In the case of, for example, interviews where sensitive data is shared, the sensitive information provided is done so voluntarily by the participants and therefore, participants willingly give informed consent to the study.

ICEBERG does not specifically ask questions about sensitive information. Confidential and the most sensitive information about Indigenous participant's relationship with the ocean and the land will not be shared (such as spiritually important sites).

7.4 Human participation

7.4.1 Indigenous and traditional knowledge

It is important to be aware that data in the project generated as a result of working with Indigenous communities may be subject to different or additional ethical considerations. Science in modern terms is often associated with western thinking based on a Eurocentric knowledge system (Aikenhead and Ogawa, 2007) and its attempts to incorporate Indigenous knowledge may be seen as a form of colonialism (Liboiron, 2021). A point of difference between these knowledge systems is that traditional knowledge is often about “ways of knowing, not what is known” and thus does not generate data (footnote 46/p. 53, Liboiron, 2021). Given the distinct nature between traditional ways of knowing and dominant science’s methodologies, the project needs to consider how to implement data principles that are tailored with indigenous rights in mind.

One such guideline is the CARE Principles for Indigenous Data Governance (<https://www.gida-global.org/care>): Data principles created to advance the legal principles underlying collective and individual data rights in the context of the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples (UNDRIP). CARE is distinctly separate from FAIR in that FAIR principles focus on increased data sharing alone, while CARE principles encourage data sharing in both a people-oriented and purpose-oriented way (Global Indigenous Data Alliance, n.d.). Without the consideration of people, data sharing alone creates tension for Indigenous Peoples and ignores power differentials and historical contexts (Global Indigenous Data Alliance, n.d.). The CARE Principles are (Global Indigenous Data Alliance, 2022):

- **Collective Benefit:** Data ecosystems shall be designed and function in ways that enable Indigenous Peoples to derive benefit from the data
- **Authority to Control:** Indigenous Peoples’ rights and interests in Indigenous data must be recognized and their authority to control such data respected
- **Responsibility:** Those working with Indigenous data have a responsibility to share how those data are used to support Indigenous Peoples’ self-determination and collective benefit
- **Ethics:** Indigenous Peoples’ rights and wellbeing should be the primary concern at all stages of the data life cycle and across the data ecosystem

Regarding the last principle of ethics, as per the ICEBERG DoA Section 4 Ethics Self-Assessment, the project will follow the ethical and methodological guidelines of the International Arctic Social Sciences Association (IASSA, 2020), and in Greenland also the Ilisimatusarfik’s guidelines for ethical research (2024) and the Inuit Circumpolar Council’s (ICC) protocols on Ethical and Equitable Engagement (ICC, 2022). These principles include:

- Responding to and supporting local communities’ needs with the research and knowledge co-produced. During consultation meetings, attending community members have highlighted a list of priority issues of concerns that ICEBERG research should address
- Respecting and including Indigenous ways of knowing: ICEBERG includes Indigenous methodologies such as storytelling, community gathering, etc.
- Respecting free, prior and informed consent (FPIC), a principle that is included in the United Nations Declaration on the Rights of Indigenous Peoples

Stakeholder engagement will follow the recommendations of:

- Integrated European Polar Research Programme (EU-PolarNet 2020)
- EU-PolarNet White paper on stakeholder engagement in polar research (Latola et al., 2020)
- A toolkit for Community Based Participatory Research in Greenland (Rink and Adler-Reimer, 2019)

The recommendations of the above resources highlight the importance of adopting a high degree of coordination among different activities to avoid stakeholders’ “research fatigue” while optimising efforts. Other

recommendations include trust building and early engagement, proper allocation of time and funding, diversity and equity in the engagement process, seeking for participation and collaboration, and careful and coordinated identification of stakeholder contact points (i.e. intermediaries). Building on these existing guidelines and protocols, ICEBERG will co-develop and implement an ethics evaluation framework, which will be presented in D4.1 Co-creation / citizen science framework and lessons learned. The ethics evaluation framework has the purpose of continuously evaluating the ICEBERG consortium’s engagement with research ethics throughout the duration of the project. Central to this framework are ‘points of co-evaluation’ over the project’s lifetime. ‘Points of co-evaluation’ are spaces and moments of engagements where different actors, such as consortium members and project partners, can come together and reflect on the ethical dimension of their work. Based on the ICEBERG project’s progress and the needs of the different people involved, the ethics evaluation framework is being adapted accordingly.

In addition, the ICEBERG Code of Conduct (D4.2) is a framework for self-regulation that includes practices for research collaboration with Indigenous communities.

7.4.2 Vulnerable groups

Citizen science is an important part of the ICEBERG project. Since participant selection among the three field site communities takes into consideration inclusiveness and aims for diverse representation, there is also a possibility that vulnerable group members will take part in the research, including people with disabilities, people facing socio-economic challenges, the elderly, and pregnant women. The participation of any vulnerable people will be based on the ability to nonetheless give informed consent.

The project will not involve individuals under 18 years of age, with the exception of 16-year-old students who are part of a class where the teacher operates a drone for marine litter mapping. The group of students will engage in a research-related activity under the strict supervision of both the teacher and the responsible partners, ensuring full compliance with ethical guidelines and obtaining the necessary consents. Having these youth participants do not lead to any additional ethical risks or worries.

In the South-West Greenland field site, ICEBERG project members will engage with the communities of Narsaq, Qaqortoq and Nanortalik. Working in a predominantly Indigenous context, the ICEBERG project follows the Ilisimatusarfik’s guidelines for ethical research (2024).

The table below presents potential risks to vulnerable groups and mitigation strategies to minimise these risks.

Table 10. Potential risks to vulnerable groups and how to mitigate them.

Potential risk	Mitigation strategy
Recalling traumatic events in relation to environmental disturbances including pollution triggered by some of the questions	Right to withdraw at any time. If wished, interviews can be carried out with the presence of a person who has the trust of the community and can intervene with culturally appropriate ways
Concern of findings disrupting traditional way of life or producing negative results about their community	Co-creation methodologies, research transparency of project goals, and open discourse about findings

Potential risk	Mitigation strategy
Concerns that time and contributions of participants will not be adequately compensated	Mechanisms in place for non-monetary and monetary formats for compensation of research participants. E.g. participation prizes and opportunity to have one's name shown as a knowledge holder
Misrepresentation of information expressed in interviews through the analysis of a researcher	Presenting/sharing research findings with interviewees who indicated in the consent form the wish to receive the results prior to publication, and giving them the opportunity to input, suggest or amend before publication. Double-checking knowledge provided non-anonymously will be practiced
Concerns may arise that a focus group participant will worry about information shared during the session being disclosed by others outside the group	Participants will be asked to keep information confidential, and open communication will be encouraged throughout the session to ensure participants feel safe discussing their concerns

The project also aims to ensure data sharing with local communities and Indigenous rights holders, and to ensure that data or the knowledge built on the collected data benefit them. Below are the strategies that will be employed by the project:

- Regular workshops and meetings with community members for feedback and to share findings
- Communities' wishes, needs and preferences will be discussed during the community consultation meetings (what research questions are relevant to different community members) in the three field sites
- Local representatives in project advisory board and feedback/evaluation meetings with advisory members throughout project process every six months
- Local pollution mitigation strategies co-produced and shared with communities
- Involvement of locals as co-authors of publications and as co-presenters at conferences if wished and if budget allows
- A joint presentation at classes at the high school at Qaqortoq (Greenland), at the University of Akureyri, at the Húsavík Knowledge Centre (Iceland) and at the University Centre in Svalbard (UNIS) (Svalbard)
- Participatory feedback sessions on the CBEM platform: Communities' wishes, needs, and preferences will be discussed
- Photographs and data will go through a local curator (training workshops provided)
- Care is taken to communicate in the language of the case study regions through translation of materials and hiring local interpreters

7.5 Artificial Intelligence (AI) and machine learning

The ICEBERG project involves machine learning and AI in several methodologies. Consortium partner, SciDrones (SCI) has created the Coastal Marine Litter Observatory (CMLO), which uses unmanned aerial systems and machine learning algorithms to automatically detect and map marine litter in coastal zones. Time-lapse cameras installed by Kiel University (CAU) will also develop a machine learning approach to analyse time-series data of field-based cameras. For modelling results with pathways and impact of pollutants in seawater, Helmholtz Centre

for Ocean Research (GEOMAR) may use AI for analyses of model results and for coding scripts for analysing model results.

As a quality assurance for AI data, human oversight is required for data validation and monitoring. For AI activities used for detecting litter on collected drone images, developers and deployers are involved in the process of training, monitoring and validating AI therefore maintaining human agency and oversight requirements. Information about the employed AI methods is publicly available on the CMLO platform website (<https://cmlo.aegean.gr/>). SCI will self-assess the trustworthiness of their AI by undertaking the Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI). Confidence level on AI decisions is also provided. For the time-lapse images and time-series datasets, these will be analysed by machine learning approaches but there will still be human oversight to help ensure that the results derived from the data are accurate. Students and teachers ("the citizens") will actively participate in developing the application for the time-lapse cameras. They will receive training in image analysis and image categorization, such as identifying types of marine litter. Humans (including local community members) perform quality checks on the cameras to ensure that the time-series data used for analysis is of high quality, accurate, and reliable.

To ensure data protection for drone images, a quality check will be conducted to identify any images that unintentionally capture individuals. While the AI does not collect, store or process personal data, it may happen that people are unintentionally captured in images during flight missions. SCI will take actions to protect anonymity by blurring or/and deleting those parts of the images. Time-lapse data will be stored and processed according to the principles of the EASA Privacy Handbook of Drone Rules for Recreational Users (https://www.easa.europa.eu/sites/default/files/dfu/privacyhandbook_en.pdf). CAU is supported by CAU Research Data Management to ensure data protection, fairness, and non-discrimination (<https://www.datamanagement.uni-kiel.de/en>).

The following guidelines for data collection and handling will be followed:

- Guidelines for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence
- Ethics By Design and Ethics of Use Approaches for Artificial Intelligence
- Assessment List for Trustworthy Artificial Intelligence (ALTAI)
- ESA (European Space Agency) Corporate Social Responsibility Code of Conduct
- EASA Privacy Handbook of Drone Rules for Recreational Users
- EU Commission - Ethics for researchers

7.5.1 Time-lapse cameras

7.5.1.1 Iceland

Certain sections of the littoral are privately owned and permits from landowners (farmers) have been requested and granted. The cameras have been / will be installed in consultation with our local collaborators and the neighbouring infrastructures have been informed. Furthermore, for camera installations in other areas, permits from the municipality (e.g., in Raufarhöfn) have been requested and granted with consultation through our local collaborators. An information letter written in Icelandic and English is attached to the cameras to inform passers-by about the project and the use of the cameras.

7.5.1.2 Greenland

Time-lapse cameras will be installed within the area of the municipality of Qaqortoq. Requests for the necessary permits have been / will be put in place when needed. An information letter written in Greenlandic and Danish is planned to be attached to the cameras to inform passers-by about the project and the use of the cameras.

7.5.1.3 Svalbard

The ICEBERG research project has been registered in the Research in Svalbard (RiS) portal. Time-lapse camera installation method has been approved by the Governor to minimize environmental risk and/or cultural damage (e.g. guy ropes are banned as they pose a risk of wildlife entanglement, see Table 11).

7.5.2 Drones

In the ICEBERG project, the drone model used is the DJI Mavic 3 Enterprise. It is a professional-grade drone designed for industrial applications, featuring a high-resolution camera, and advanced RTK positioning for precision mapping and inspection tasks. It offers enhanced flight performance, extended battery life, and robust data security, making it ideal for surveying and mapping operations. The DJI Mavic 3 Enterprise falls under the C1 category of drones, with a take-off weight of approximately 920 grammes.

The use of drones in Iceland and Greenland is subject to strict regulations aimed at ensuring safe, responsible, and ethical operations. Adherence to these regulations is essential to uphold privacy, environmental protection, and safety, when drones are used for research, commercial, or personal purposes. This section outlines the regulatory framework and ethical considerations for drone use in both Iceland and Greenland, including the specific rules and obligations for operators.

7.5.2.1 Iceland

As a member of the European Union Aviation Safety Agency (EASA), Iceland follows EASA's harmonized regulations for the operation of drones. In addition, Iceland also has regulations that are country specific. Therefore, the key legal and ethical considerations for drone operators in Iceland must reflect both EASA guidelines and local regulations enforced by the Icelandic Transport Authority (ICETRA). Drone operations within the ICEBERG project fall under the Open category under EASA.

Responsible partners will follow the following key regulatory and ethical considerations:

- registering the drone with the Icelandic Civil Aviation Administration (ICAA) as the drone weights more than 250 grammes, and having an ID attached to it,
- obtaining a license as the drone weights more than 250 grammes,
- flying below 120 metres above ground level to avoid conflicts with manned aircraft,
- no flights within 2 kilometres from any international airports and 1,5 of any other airports,
- no flights within 50 metres of any building in urban areas, and 150 metres in rural areas.
- protecting wildlife by following environmental guidelines when flying the drone nearby sensitive wildlife areas.

7.5.2.2 Greenland

Drone regulations in Greenland are specific due to Greenland's status outside the EU. Both the Danish Civil Aviation Authority (CAA Denmark) and the Greenlandic Transport Authority are involved in regulating drone operations in Greenland, but the primary authority is CAA Denmark. The Greenlandic Transport Authority addresses more localized concerns within Greenland, especially regarding environmental protection and specific local restrictions. Specific ethical considerations apply due to Greenland's unique environment and cultural heritage.

EASA licenses (from the EU) are not recognized in Greenland, meaning that responsible partners need additional permits from the Greenlandic local authorities. They will comply with Greenland's national legislation, as outlined in BL 9-4 under the Danish Air Navigation Act. This includes the following rules:

- drones must stay at least 5 km from public aerodromes and 8 km from military airbases,
- the minimum distance from built-up areas and major public roads is 150 m,
- drones must not fly higher than 100 m above the ground,

- the three sensitive nature reserves in Greenland (the National Park of Greenland, Melville Bay and Angujaartorfiup Nunaa, southwest of Kangerlussuaq) that are referred to in BL 7-16 will not be overflowed.

Additionally, responsible partners will not film or pursue polar bears, as stipulated in §4, 4 of Executive Order No. 3 of 14 September 2018. Ethical operation in Greenland involves strict adherence to these rules to protect both human safety and wildlife.

7.5.3 Impacts on using drones and time-lapse cameras

Along with the intended use of AI and capturing plastic pollution in images for the ICEBERG project, there is also the possibility for unintentional outcomes beyond human control and scope of the project. Therefore, the ICEBERG project has identified some of the potential negative social and environmental impacts of using AI and compiled the table below to discuss how to optimally minimise these impacts. The cases highlighted in the table below are not exhaustive.

Table 11. Potential negative impact of use and handline drones, time-lapse cameras and how to minimize them

Potential negative social and/or environmental impacts	Plans to minimize negative impacts
<p>The time lapse cameras are powered by batteries that may pose a potential risk to the environment if not handled properly</p>	<p>To ensure safety, caution has been / is being exercised to protect the batteries from any external damage. The batteries are secured in a waterproof, hard plastic box to protect them from external factors such as animals, moisture, and water. This box is fastened to a tripod leg using weatherproof adhesive tape and a tensioning strap, positioned approx. 20 - 30 cm above the ground. The tripod itself is anchored to the ground with a tensioning strap and an anchoring system. With these precautions, we reduced the risk of battery displacement or loss</p>
<p>Images of humans could be unintentionally captured during the usage of drones and time-lapse cameras</p>	<p>Drones: Following Iceland’s privacy laws, we will not capture images or videos of people. However, if unforeseen images containing people do occur, project members responsible for this process will Ensure anonymity by blurring or deleting such parts of drone-captured images.</p> <p>Time-lapse cameras: Given the automatic nature of the time-lapse approach, manually blurring specific parts of images is impractical. With 17 cameras capturing one image per hour over the project’s duration, reviewing all images manually is not manageable. Instead, blurring/deleting parts of the images will be applied only to training and validation data. Reasonable measures will be taken to minimize the risks associated with privacy concerns. Output maps will focus solely on litter detection (raw data will not be shared)</p>
<p>Injury or property damage/ damage to landscapes or wildlife</p>	<p>Drones: Efficient and detailed training for participants, routine maintenance and recovery of drones if such event happens</p>

Potential negative social and/or environmental impacts	Plans to minimize negative impacts
	Time-lapse cameras: to prevent potential harm to animals, researchers avoid using sharp or meshed components, such as nets. There are also no fine cords or small parts that could entangle animals or be ingested by them. The connecting cable between camera and external batteries is securely fastened to a tripod leg with weatherproof adhesive tape and cable ties to ensure that it does not hang loose

7.6 Organic and inorganic samples

All activities involving snow, water and sediment collection as part of ICEBERG have been registered in the Research in Svalbard (RiS). ICEBERG project researchers will strive to collect organic and inorganic samples from the local environment and ecosystems in a low-impact way to avoid potential risks. Organic samples in ICEBERG are materials derived from living organisms, such as plants, animal-based food items, and bacteria. Inorganic samples collected and used in ICEBERG are derived from sediments, snow, ice, and water.

7.6.1 Sediment sampling

- Svalbard: all soil and marine sediment sampling plans are reported to the Governor of Svalbard in keeping with applicable deadlines. Sampling activities are carried out in accordance with Svalbard Environmental Protection Act and, in the case of sampling within protected areas (such as South Spitsbergen National Park), based on relevant permits issued by the Governor of Svalbard.
- Iceland: soil sampling will happen in state-owned territories in 2025. No permit is needed.

7.6.2 Food samples

To assess chemical contamination in foods relevant to local diets, samples of animal-origin foodstuffs (including seafood, birds, and mammals) are collected from local stores, professional fishermen, or by a veterinarian at abattoirs after slaughtering in Iceland and Greenland. The selection of specific food matrices and the required number of samples will be guided by a dietary survey conducted among local populations. This anonymous survey was distributed both electronically and in paper format by local members of the ICEBERG project. The electronic version was promoted via Facebook over a two-month period. Participants were informed of the study's purpose and gave their consent prior to completing the questionnaire. No personally identifiable information was collected, and all responses were securely stored in .xls format (approx. 20 MB) on institutional network drives.

Food items such as cod liver, haddock liver, Arctic char, fish fillet, shark meat, lamb meat, guillemot, and wild berries have been/will be selected for analysis based on their frequency of consumption in local diets and/or their potential for contaminant bioaccumulation. In Greenland, the selection of food item samples for analysis will be based on survey results and carried out in collaboration with the local coordinator and the Self-Sufficiency Department of the Government of Greenland. Food item samples for analysis from Iceland were selected based on survey findings, in coordination with the local coordinator. Upon reception at the ONIRIS laboratory, all samples will be securely stored until analysis. Analyses will be conducted using chromatographic techniques coupled to mass spectrometry, covering key persistent organic pollutants (POPs) such as polychlorinated biphenyls (PCBs), organochlorine pesticides (OCPs), dioxins/furans, and per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances

(PFAS). Suspect screening will also be applied to selected samples to identify additional contaminants of emerging concern.

All targeted analyses will be performed under ISO 17025-accredited methods by the National Reference Laboratory. Samples will be stored at the ONIRIS laboratory under controlled conditions until the end of the project and destroyed in compliance with applicable regulations. In Greenland, ethical clearance is sought through submission to the Ethical Committee for health research at Greenland's Centre for Health Research (GCHR), and Genetic Resources Greenland (for food samples) ensuring all protocols adhere to national and institutional ethical standards. The involvement of the exporting country's competent authority, such as the Icelandic and Greenlandic Food and Veterinary Authority, will ensure compliance with French import regulations. These authorities are responsible for certifying that the samples meet the necessary sanitary and phytosanitary standards, which is a prerequisite for entry into the EU.

7.6.3 Toxicological impact analysis of micro- and nano-plastics and other contaminants (PFAS) on human digestive health

The work on in vitro human cells will be performed in WP2 using commercially available human cell lines. To this end, ICEBERG considers intestinal cell co-culture models, simulating the epithelium-mucus axis in the human upper and lower gastro-intestinal tract (Caco-2/HT29-MTX and T84/LS174T, respectively) and HepaRG cell line, known to exhibit many characteristics similar to primary human hepatocytes. The impact on several biological processes (e.g. cell viability, barrier function, inflammatory response, genotoxicity, oxidative stress, activation of nuclear receptors) will be assessed.

Cell derivatives will be stored until maximum two years after the end of the project, after which they will be discarded. All information is property of the provider (European Collection of Authenticated Cell Cultures (ECACC) or Biopredic) and non-disclosed to the owner, with exception of the information that is publicly disclosed by means of websites (<https://www.culturecollections.org.uk/>, <https://wepredic.com/en/biopredic>).

The following guidelines will be followed for data collection and handling:

- DFG Guide to Good Scientific Practice
- Nagoya Protocol
- Research in Svalbard (RiS) guidelines

7.6.4 Impacts of working with organic and inorganic samples

These potential risks are described in Table 12. Standard protocols for collecting organic samples, which adhere to international guidelines, include preparation, site selection, proper sample collection, post-collection care, detailed documentation, appropriate storage and transport. Biological material transfer documents may be required for transporting of samples between countries.

Table 12. Potential risk to local environment/ecosystem and humans and how to mitigate the risks

Potential risks to local environment and ecosystems	Mitigation strategy
Damage or disturbance (e.g. to plants) caused by sample collection	Careful selection of sampling locations and reducing sample sizes to the necessary minimum. In the case of soil sampling, backfilling sampling spots
Polluting sampling area with mismanaged sampling equipment (e.g. filters, vials, nets) or chemicals (e.g. acids)	Adjusting sampling procedures to Arctic conditions to eliminate or reduce equipment loss and contamination risk

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9 Appendices

9.1 Appendix 1: Data questionnaire for partners

Appendix Table 1. Questions about data management and ethics answered by all partners.

Questions about data	Explanation
1. What is the purpose of the data you are collecting/generating?	Describe briefly how the data fulfils project objectives.
2. What type of data are you collecting/generating?	Describe briefly what kind of data you are collecting. You may indicate whether the data is quantitative (e.g. marine litter dataset) or qualitative (e.g. interviews).
3. What is the format of the data?	Indicate the expected format of your data (file extension). E.g. interview audio transcripts could be in formats mp3, mp4, wav; while GIS maps could be in formats GeoJSON, tif, kml.
4. What standards apply to the data?	List any standards that the data adheres to. E.g. ISO, metadata standards, standardised vocabularies, standards-based data description to promote findability and interoperability of your datasets. Do not answer "none": If no standards are used, specify how metadata is created/used vocabularies are made available.
5. Does the data collection method follow a standard protocol?	List any standard methodological protocols with citations where possible.
6. Is the data primary or secondary data?	Indicate whether the data is primary (collected by you for the first time and has not undergone analysis or processing yet) or secondary data (whether/how you are reusing existing data, perhaps from another project you worked on).
7. What is the origin of the data?	Indicate where the data was generated or collected e.g. the field work environment if biogeophysical data, or the community name if oral/citizen-sourced data.
8. Who is the data owner?	Data generated is typically owned by the project and your institution. However, you may also need to consider Indigenous knowledge holders' rights to any Indigenous cultural data collected/generated.

Questions about data	Explanation
9. Where is the data stored during the project?	List all file systems that the data would be stored in throughout the duration of the project. We are particularly interested in whether the data is stored by any third party (e.g. Open Access mapping software).
10. If the data is stored/handled by third parties, what is their data protection agreement?	You may link to the terms and agreement page on their website if available. For example, the interactive community based monitoring platform uses UMAP and their data protection policy can be found on the website.
11. How long will the data be stored for?	Your institution may have rules regarding data retention and how long data can be stored before termination, particularly personal data.
12. Are any quality assurance/control methods applied to the data during or post-collection/generation?	Describe any methods used for QA/QC throughout the entire data collection process. E.g. before: training/competency sessions for community participants, during: QA/QC standards for data collection in your field, after: running diagnostics in data processing software
13. Do you plan to reuse the data generated from the project? 13a. Describe any ways that you plan to reuse the data. 13b. What is the reuse value of the data to other researchers/third parties?	For example, you may wish to compare the project case studies data to other locations you have studied, or future locations you plan to study.
14. Is the data open access? 14a. Under which license will data be opened? (recommended: CC BY 4.0 "Attribution 4.0 International") 14b. What additional documentation (e.g., readme files) will be provided to make the data reuse possible? 14c. If access to (open) data is restricted, how the access is controlled? 14d. If data cannot be Open Access, explain why.	The data is expected to be open access where possible, however there may be restrictions (e.g. proprietary restricted data, data requiring license/special software to access, data that needs to be anonymised for privacy reasons). Note: metadata should always be published even if the data will not be, (preferably) licensed with CC0 "No Rights Reserved".
15. Will you deposit/archive data outputs/metadata in a public repository?	Data should be made available for reuse in accordance with the FAIR principles (if possible).

Questions about data	Explanation
<p>15a. List the repositories you plan to use. E.g. Zenodo, Open Science Framework, any open access repositories specific to your field.</p> <p>15b. Will the planned repositories provide the (meta)data with a persistent identifier (PID) such as DOI or URN?</p> <p>15c. In addition to data, are there any other possible research outputs (e.g., code, software, samples), and how will you make these available for reuse in accordance with the FAIR principles?</p>	
<p>16. Do you plan to collect personal data from participants? If so, what is the protocol and relevant regulation?</p> <p>16a. If yes, who is the data controller?</p> <p>16b. If there is a data processor, who is the data processor?</p> <p>16c. Is there a data processing agreement in place?</p>	<p>Using and handling of personal data must be in compliance with EU directives on privacy protection, as well as country specific regulations. Describe your protocol for protecting participants' personal data (e.g. anonymisation of personal information). Also list any relevant data protection regulations specific to your institution's country (e.g. German Federal Data Protection Act, Hellenic Data Protection Authority, Spanish Data Protection and Digital Rights Act)</p>
<p>17. Does your organisation have a protocol for handling and secure storage of sensitive data?</p>	<p>If this information is not available publicly (e.g. on institution website), you will need to find out from your data protection officer.</p>
<p>18. What are the regulations for data protection for your case study if not under EU directive?</p>	<p>List any relevant regulations here.</p>
<p>19. Does your institution have a data protection officer?</p> <p>19a. If no, who is responsible for data management at your institution?</p> <p>19b. What resources are needed for research data management (RDM)</p>	<p>Provide the contact of your institution's data protection office and/or competent authorities that ensure compliance with rules and standards for data protection.</p>

Questions about data	Explanation
and to make the data FAIR (are there any costs?)?	
20. Does your institution have an ethics committee?	List your institution's ethics committees and/or competent authorities that ensure compliance with rules and standards around research involving people/animals.
21. Do you need to go through an ethics clearance / ethics approval / ethics certificate / statement from an ethics committee?	List the ethics committee steps you need to go through.
22. Which ethical governance procedures are you requested to follow?	List any existing ethical regulations (national laws, institutional guidelines etc.)
23. How do you ensure the voluntariness and the informed consent?	
24. Are you working with vulnerable groups (i.e. Indigenous Peoples, children)? 24a. Are there any potential risks for vulnerable groups or cultural heritage resulting from your work? 24b. How to mitigate, minimize these risks? 24c. How do you ensure sharing data with local communities and Indigenous communities? How do you ensure that data benefit them?	List the vulnerable groups you are working with. Note: cultural heritage might be at risk even in cases when the research doesn't involve human participants (e.g., sacred sites)
25. What ethical guidelines do you follow?	
26. Are there any potential risks to the local environment and ecosystems?	List the potential risks.
27. In case of transporting samples between countries, which agreements do you follow?	

Questions about data	Explanation
28. In case you use AI, how do you ensure human agency, oversight, transparency and accountability?	
29. How do you ensure data protection, fairness, and non-discrimination?	
30. Identify potential negative social and/or environmental impacts (e.g., decision making, profiling, surveillance) and explain how they will be minimized	
31. If you use time-lapse cameras, drones, how do you store and process data in accordance with EU GDPR?	

9.2 Appendix 2: Information Form

INFORMATION FOR PARTICIPANTS – ICEBERG Project

ICEBERG Consortium partners:

University of Oulu (Finland); Associacao Para O Desenvolvimento Do Atlantic – Atlantic International Research Centre (Portugal); Barcelona Supercomputing Center - Centro Nacional De Supercomputación (Spain); Fundacja forScience (Poland); GEOMAR Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel (Germany); GFZ Helmholtz Centre for Geosciences (Germany); UFZ Helmholtz Centre for Environmental Research (Germany); ONIRIS-Ecole Nationale Vétérinaire, Agroalimentaire et de l'alimentation de Nantes-Atlantique (France); Consiglio Nazionale Delle Ricerche (Italy); KASKAS Media OY (Finland); Christian-Albrechts-Universitaet zu Kiel (Germany); University of Lapland (Finland); INRAE-Ecole Nationale Vétérinaire, Agroalimentaire et de l'alimentation (France); SCIDRONES P.C. (Greece); Stefansson Arctic Institute (Iceland); Women Of The Arctic RY (Finland)

The ICEBERG research project (2024-2026) is funded by the European Union.

You are invited to participate in a research project. Before accepting, please take the time to read this document which presents the conditions of participation. Do not hesitate to ask any questions that you may have to the person who presents this document.

Research objectives

The ICEBERG project studies ocean and coastal pollution and creates governance and resilience strategies with Arctic communities in Kalaallit Nunaat (Greenland), Iceland and Svalbard. The ICEBERG project has 3 goals:

- 1) to study the sources, types and spread of ocean and coastal pollution - like plastics, ship emissions, wastewater - from long-distance transport via the open ocean and atmosphere or from regional sources such as industry and from thawing glaciers, snow, and ice;
- 2) to assess the effects of pollution on the environment and on people and communities;
- 3) to co-design strategies with communities to reduce pollution (mitigation), make communities less vulnerable to pollution (adaptation), and develop policy recommendations for pollution-control governance.

Your participation in the research

Your participation in this research includes a semi-structured interview or focus group to discuss your observations and experiences with pollution and environmental changes, and their effects on local practices, food security, well-being, health, identity, and infrastructure. We will also discuss how regulations influence pollution in your area and how pollution impacts different groups such as women, men, elders, youth. Additionally, we will discuss how communities and researchers collaborate. The interview or focus group will include a participatory interactive or paper mapping activity, allowing you to highlight areas of concern regarding environmental disturbances. The interview will last 30-45 minutes, and the focus group about an hour. With your permission, the interview will be audio-recorded to facilitate transcription. The time and place will be arranged according to your preferences.

You are invited to join a year-round citizen science activity to detect and map coastal marine litter using drones and time-lapse cameras. We will provide training in drone operation, camera setup, data collection, and analysis, including identifying and categorizing marine litter. You can suggest key beach areas to monitor, assist with camera setup and check-ups, and conduct drone flights to track litter. The data will help create maps of hotspot areas for targeted environmental interventions like clean-ups. The citizen science activities are separate from interviews and focus groups, and will take place during the participants own time and depending on their own activity. Your participation in the citizen science activities is entirely optional. If you choose not to participate in the interviews and/or focus groups, you can still fully engage in the citizen science activities.

Benefits, risks or possible disadvantages of your participation

There is no particular risk in participating in this projects. It is possible that there are no direct benefits of participating in this study for you particularly, but the mitigation, adaptation and governance strategies developed during this study may benefit your area in the future. Participating in this research gives you an opportunity to share and discuss confidentially your personal observations and experiences of pollution, environmental changes and disturbances, including how they affect local nature and practices, food, health, identity, as well as the impact of regulations and policies on pollution in your area. It is possible that telling your story gives rise to moving or uncomfortable thoughts or memories. If this happens, do not hesitate to talk to the person conducting the interview. Confidential and the most sensitive information about your relationship with ocean and the land will not be shared (such as spiritually important sites).

Compensation

Travel costs due to your participation in this research will be compensated. Participating in this research will not incur any extra costs on you. If you would like to read the scientific publications (articles, posters) and/or reports that will emerge from the project, we can send them to you upon request.

Voluntary participation and right of withdraw

Your participation in the ICEBERG project is entirely voluntary. You can terminate your participation and withdraw your already given consent at any time without negative consequences or prejudice and without having to justify your decision. If you decide to end your participation, it is important to inform the researchers whose contact details are included in this document. Upon withdrawing your

consent to participate all personal information about you will be destroyed. However, the research data collected so far may be used in the research.

Privacy and data management - Personal data included in the research materials

In this research, personal data like name, signature, contact information, age, occupation, gender, voice (if audio recorded) will be collected through interviews, focus groups, and maps.

Lawful basis of processing this personal data is Article 6(1) of the EU General Data Protection Regulation citing scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes. Sensitive personal data concerning most indirectly health related (not medical data) and racial or ethnic origin gathered from the interviews and focus groups will be processed in the study. Sensitive data is processed on the legal basis of scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes, as outlined in Article 9(2) of the General Data Protection Regulation.

Your personal data is confidential. The following steps will be taken to ensure the confidentiality of the information provided by you:

- Your name will not appear in any report and/or scientific publication. A code will be assigned to each interviewee and only the researchers will know his/her/they identity. Only this code will appear in scientific publications. Only if you wish your name to be cited in recognition of your role as knowledge holder, knowledge bearer of nature-related knowledge in the scientific publications (articles, posters) and/or reports that will emerge from the ICEBERG project, we will mention your name.
- We will record the interview only with your agreement.
- Personal data processed in IT systems: i) username ; ii) password. Processing of direct identifiers: i) direct identifiers will be removed in the analysis phase
- The research material will be archived without identifiers. The material will be archived for 10 years at each participating research organization. Only the research team has access to the data and only for scientific analysis.
- Research materials, including data and records, will be kept in a secure location. Recordings will be transcribed and the transcripts will be destroyed, along with any personal information, 10 years after the project ends. Only non-identifying data will be retained after this period.
- No personal data will be transferred or disclosed to recipients outside the research group.
- The University of Oulu, Finland is leader of this research project. Consortium members mentioned above have all access to the data for non-commercial, scientific purpose only. Data transfers to Iceland are based on the adequacy decision made by the EU.

Rights and Exceptions

- You have the right to obtain information on whether or not personal data concerning you are being processed in the project, as well as the data being processed. You can also request a copy of the personal data undergoing processing (GDPR Article 15). If there are inaccuracies or errors in your personal data undergoing processing, you have the right to request their rectification or supplementation (GDPR Article 16).
- You can request the erasure of your personal data on the grounds specified in GDPR Article 17 on Right to erasure and you can limit the processing of your personal data for reasons cited in GDPR Article 18 on Right to restriction of processing.
- You can request to receive the personal data you have submitted to the Universities (GDPR Article 20).
You have the right to object to processing your personal data. The University will no longer have the right to process your personal data unless it can demonstrate compelling legitimate grounds for the processing that override the interests, rights and freedoms of the data subject, or unless it is necessary for the establishment, exercise or defense of legal claims. The University can continue processing your personal data also when necessary for the performance of a task carried out for reasons of the public interest (GDPR Article 21).
- In certain individual cases, derogations from the rights described above in this section “Your rights as a data subject”, and exceptions to these rights may be made on the basis of the GDPR and the Finnish Data Protection Act, insofar as the rights render impossible or seriously impair the achievement of scientific or historical research purposes or statistical purposes. The need for derogations will always be assessed on a case-by-case basis.

Data Controller: University of Oulu, Pentti Kaiterankatu 1, P. O. Box 8000, 90014 OULU, Contact of Data Protection Officer: dpo@oulu.fi.

If you have any questions about data privacy issues, or the rights of participants, or wish to withdraw from the research, **you can contact the ICEBERG project coordinating team: Thora Herrmann, thora.herrmann@oulu.fi, ph: +49 173 1985 042; Élise Lépy, elise.lepy@oulu.fi**

Complaints or Criticism

You have the right to lodge a complaint with the Data Protection Ombudsman’s Office if you think your personal data has been processed in violation of applicable data protection laws.

Contact details: Data Protection Ombudsman’s Office (Tietosuoja-valtuutetun toimisto)

Street address: Lintulahdenkuja 4, 00530 Helsinki Postal address: PL 800, 00531 Helsinki, Finland

Switchboard: +358 29 566 6700 Registry: +358 29 566 6768 E-mail: tietosuoja@om.fi

9.2 Appendix 3: Written Consent Form

PARTICIPANT WRITTEN CONSENT FORM – ICEBERG Project

Declaration of Consent

- I understand that I can take my time to think before agreeing or not to participate in the research project.
- I can ask questions to the research team and demand satisfactory answers.
- I understand that by participating in this research project, I am not relieving researchers of their responsibilities.
- I understand that my name will not appear in any report and/or scientific publication. Only, if I wish my name to be cited in recognition of my role as knowledge holder, knowledge bearer of environmental-related knowledge in the scientific publications (articles, posters) and/or reports that will emerge from the ICEBERG project, my name will be mentioned.
 - Yes, I like my name to be cited.
- I authorize the researchers to audio-record the interview. Yes No
- I authorize the researchers to distribute the photographic material that I have provided to them, knowing that the material will be accompanied by a credit to the author of the work (respect of copyright) and only used for non-commercial, scientific purpose.
- I understand that the recording of the interview (if taken) will be accessible only by the researcher/s conducting the interview and the person producing the transcript. I agree that the transcript or word-for-word notes will be accessible (please select):
 - only to the interviewer/s and the transcription assistant,
 - only to the core team conducting this part of the research within ICEBERG.
- I have understood that my participation in this research is voluntary and that I may, whenever, announce that I will no longer participate in it. In such case the research data collected so far may be used for the research.
- I have received sufficiently information regarding the research and any questions have been answered. I have understood the information that has been given to me and I wish to participate in the research. I have read the Privacy Notice regarding this research

Signatures

I, the undersigned _____ give my freely given and informed consent to participate in the ICEBERG research project. I read the *Information For Participants* regarding this research project and understood the purpose, nature, advantages, risks and disadvantages of the project. I am satisfied with the explanations, clarifications and answers that the researcher has provided me, if any, regarding my participation in this project.

Signature of the participant

Date and Place

A brief summary of the research results will be sent to participants who request it. Please provide the address where you would like to receive the document. Results will not be available until 2026. If this address changes before then, please inform the researcher of the new address to ensure you receive the summary.

The address (e-mail or postal) to which I would like to receive a short summary of the research results is:

I explained the purpose, nature, benefits, risks and disadvantages of the research project to the participant. I answered the questions to the best of my knowledge and checked the participant's understanding.

Signature of the researcher

Date and Place

Additional Information

If you have any questions or wish to withdraw from the research, please contact the ICEBERG project coordinating team: Thora Herrmann, thora.herrmann@oulu.fi, ph.+49 173-1985-042 or Élise Lépy, elise.lepy@oulu.fi

This document has been made in duplicate, one for the research participant and one for the researcher.

9.4 Appendix 4: Written Consent Form for Youth

WRITTEN CONSENT FORM for parental authority or its representative – ICEBERG Project

Declaration of the holder of parental authority or its representative.

- I understand that my child (or the person I represent) can take time to think before agreeing or not to participate in the research project.
- I understand that my child (or the person I represent) can ask questions to the research team and demand satisfactory answers.
- I understand that by participating in this research project, my child (or the person I represent) is not relieving researchers of their responsibilities.
- I understand that my child's name (or the name of the person I represent) will not appear in any report and/or scientific publication.
- I authorize the researchers to record my child (or the person I represent) voice during the interview.
 - Yes No
- I understand that the recording of the interview with my child or the person I represent (if taken) will be accessible only by the researcher/s conducting the interview and the person producing the transcript. I agree that the transcript or word-for-word notes will be accessible (please select):
 - only to the interviewer/s and the transcription assistant,
 - only to the core team conducting this part of the research within ICEBERG.
- I authorize the researchers to distribute the photographic material that my child (or the person I represent) has provided to them, knowing that the material will be accompanied by a credit to the author of the work (respect of copyright) and only used for non-commercial, scientific purpose.
- I have understood that my child's participation in this research is voluntary and that my child (or the person I represent) may, whenever, announce that he/she/they will no longer participate in it. In such case the research data collected so far may be used for the research.

Signatures

I, the undersigned [Surname, First name] _____ give my freely given and informed consent that the person I represent participates in the ICEBERG research project under the conditions set out therein. I read the *Information For Participants* regarding this research project and understood the purpose, nature, advantages, risks and disadvantages of the project. I am satisfied with the explanations, clarifications and answers that the researcher has provided me, if any, regarding the participation in this project.

Signature of legal representative

Date and Place

Assent of minor

- I understand that I can take my time to think before agreeing or not to participate in the research project.
- I can ask questions to the research team and demand satisfactory answers.
- I understand that by participating in this research project, I am not relieving researchers of their responsibilities.
- I understand that my name will not appear in any report and/or scientific publication.
- I authorize the researchers to capture and record my image and voice during my participation in the project, including during my interview. Yes No
- I understand that the recording of the interview (if taken) will be accessible only by the researcher/s conducting the interview and the person producing the transcript. I agree that the transcript or word-for-word notes will be accessible (please select):
 - only to the interviewer/s and the transcription assistant,
 - only to the core team conducting this part of the research within ICEBERG.
- I authorize the researchers to distribute the photographic material that I have provided to them, knowing that the material will be accompanied by a credit to the author of the work (respect of copyright) and only used for non-commercial, scientific purpose.

- I have understood that my participation in this research is voluntary and that I may, whenever, announce that I will no longer participate in it. In such case the research data collected so far may be used for the research.
- I have received sufficiently information regarding the research and any questions have been answered. I have understood the information that has been given to me and I wish to participate in the research. I have read the Privacy Notice regarding this research

Signatures

I, the undersigned _____ give my freely given and informed consent to participate in the ICEBERG research project. I read the *Information For Participants* regarding this research project and understood the purpose, nature, advantages, risks and disadvantages of the project. I am satisfied with the explanations, clarifications and answers that the researcher has provided me, if any, regarding my participation in this project.

Signature of the participant

Date and Place

A summary of the research results will be sent to participants who request it. Please provide the address where you would like to receive the document. If this address changes before then, please inform the researcher of the new address to ensure you receive the summary.

The address (e-mail or postal) to which I would like to receive a summary of the research results is:

Commitment of the researcher

I explained the purpose, nature, benefits, risks and disadvantages of the research project to the participant. I answered the questions to the best of my knowledge and checked the participant's understanding.

Signature of the researcher

Date and Place

Additional Information

If you have any questions or wish to withdraw from the research, please contact the ICEBERG project coordinating team: Thora Herrmann, thora.herrmann@oulu.fi, ph.+49 173-1985-042 or Élise Lépy, elise.lepy@oulu.fi

This document has been made in duplicate, one for the legal representative of the research participant and one for the researcher.